

Deliverable D4.1

LUMEN Data Mesh Architecture Framework

Authors	Julien Homo, Kévin Darty, Luca De Santis, Paweł Marciniak, Yann Le Franc, Dieter Theiler
Submission Date	27.06.2025
Due Date	30.06.2025
Lead beneficiary	Foxcub
Corresponding WP	WP4
Deliverable Identifier	D4.1
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15752126
Project Title	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
Project Acronym	LUMEN
Project No.	101187940
Start Date	01.01.2025
End Date	31.12.2027
Call	HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01

Disclaimer: LUMEN is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement no. 101187940. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only

and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor REA can be held responsible for them.

This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Version History

Version	Name	Comments
0.1	Julien Homo, Kévin Darty	Initial draft
0.2	Luca De Santis, Paweł Marciniak, Yann Le Franc, Dieter Theiler, Julien Homo, Kévin Darty, Thomas Klebel, Simone Kopeinik, Elena Sokolova	Internal review
0.3	Christelle Plerkot, Matthieu Chavant, Pierre Poulain, Violaine Louvet, Sandrine Layrisse, Moritz Schubotz, Fotis Mystakopoulos	Community review
0.4	Julien Homo, Kévin Darty	Intermediate version
0.5	Luca De Santis, Paweł Marciniak, Yann Le Franc, Dieter Theiler, Julien Homo, Kévin Darty, Christelle Plerkot, Simone Kopeinik, Silvio Peroni, Moritz Schubotz	WP cross review
0.6	Julien Homo, Kévin Darty	Intermediate version
0.7	Christelle Plerkot, Paweł Marciniak	Final review
1.0	Julien Homo, Kévin Darty	Approved version

List of Acronyms

Terminology/ Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDA	AI Driven Discovery Assistant
API	Application Programming Interface
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CSV	Comma-Separated Value

Terminology/ Acronym	Description
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DCS	Data Contract Specification
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EASY DATA	EARth SYstem Data Repository
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
IDSA	International Data Spaces
JATS-XML	Journal Article Tag Suite - Extensible Markup Language
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LUMIS	LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics
MDML	Mathdoc Digital Mathematics Library
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (German National Research Data Infrastructure)
NIH	National Institutes of Health (USA)
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ODCS	Open Data Contract Standard
ODPS	Open Data Product Specification
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCRE	Semantic Content Retrieval Engine
SKG-IF	Scientific Knowledge Graph Interchange Format
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UML	Unified Modeling Language
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Table of Contents

Deliverable D4.1.....	1
LUMEN Data Mesh Architecture Framework.....	1
Executive Summary.....	6
0. Definitions.....	8
1. Introduction.....	13
1.1 Context and motivation.....	13
1.2 Scope of the document.....	16
2. Understanding the LUMEN Data Mesh.....	16
2.1 What is a data mesh?.....	16
2.2 Federation and decentralisation in LUMEN.....	20
2.3 Main data mesh concepts.....	23
2.3.1 What is a data product?.....	23
2.3.2 What is a data source?.....	25
2.3.3 What is a data contract?.....	26
2.4 Core architectural principles.....	31
2.5 Main architectural layers.....	33
3. Implementing the LUMEN Data Mesh.....	40
3.1 Connected Communities Ecosystem.....	40
3.1.1 Exposing the data products.....	40
3.1.2 Connecting the data sources.....	43
3.1.3 Formalising the data contracts.....	45
3.2 Common Discovery Infrastructure.....	52
3.2.1 The White-Label Discovery Platform.....	52
3.2.2 The LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (LUMIS).....	55
3.2.3 The Meta-Search Engine.....	56
3.2.4 Other LUMEN common components.....	57
3.3 Federated Data Sharing Governance.....	58
3.3.1 The governance model.....	59
3.3.2 Structure and functions of the governance layer.....	60
3.3.3 Operational link between governance and implementation.....	62
3.4 Infrastructure & Scalability considerations.....	62
3.4.1 Distributed Infrastructure Principles.....	62
3.4.2 EOSC Integration.....	64
3.4.3 Cloud deployment for LUMEN components.....	66
4. Conclusion & next steps.....	68
4.1 Key takeaways.....	68
4.2 Next steps.....	68
References.....	70
Annex 1. Extended Glossary and Conceptual Notes.....	74

Executive Summary

Scientific research is increasingly dependent on heterogeneous, distributed, and rapidly evolving datasets. Traditional centralized approaches, such as data warehouses or monolithic repositories, face significant limitations in scalability, interoperability, and cross-community collaboration. These paradigms often lead to data silos, making it difficult for researchers to discover, access, and reuse relevant information efficiently. In response to these challenges, LUMEN introduces a federated and decentralized data mesh architecture that facilitates seamless data discovery, sharing, and reuse across multiple scientific disciplines. This approach aligns with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), ensuring that scientific data remains structured, interoperable, and accessible within a governed framework. This document defines the architectural foundations of the LUMEN data mesh, outlining the vision, guiding principles, and operational mechanisms that will structure the technical implementation across the project.

At the core of LUMEN's architecture are three fundamental layers. First, the **Connected Communities Ecosystem** ensures that each scientific domain maintains ownership and control over its data products—well-defined, FAIR-compliant data assets published for reuse, while adhering to common federation rules. This layer allows data providers to expose standardized, high-quality scientific resources such as datasets, software, author profiles or semantic artefacts while remaining autonomous in their governance. The second pillar, the **Common Discovery Infrastructure**, provides a suite of domain-agnostic discovery assets, including the **White-Label Discovery Platform**, the **Meta-Search Engine**, and AI-driven discovery services such as chatbots and recommendation engines. This layer also integrates with the **LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (LUMIS)**, which facilitates the creation and management of FAIR-by-design semantic artefacts, supports metadata alignment ensuring semantic interoperability across the various data products. The third layer, **Federated Data Sharing Governance**, establishes common policies for data sharing, metadata structuring, and interoperability, ensuring alignment with EOSC standards and best practices.

LUMEN's data mesh architecture supports several key technical capabilities and practical use cases, building upon principles pioneered in large-scale data ecosystems to decentralize data ownership and foster domain-driven interoperability. Its federated architecture enables **meta-search and knowledge discovery**, facilitating cross-disciplinary searches, semantic enrichment, and intelligent linking of scientific resources such as publications, datasets, and software. This enrichment goes beyond identifier-based connections: it aims to support concept-based navigation and semantic alignment, enabling users to understand relationships between variables, concepts, or entities across heterogeneous resources. While technically ambitious, this vision is progressively pursued through **FAIR semantic artefacts** and **AI-assisted processes**. A core element of this approach is the adoption of **data contracts**, extending the data mesh paradigm by formalising a mechanism that was not explicitly defined in its early formulations. These contracts define the structure, access rules, and quality metrics

of shared resources, enabling trusted, machine-readable agreements that ensure FAIR compliance and cross-domain interoperability. Furthermore, **LUMIS** enhances metadata quality and interoperability, while LUMEN's **progressive integration model** supports the gradual adoption of APIs and structured data exchanges, allowing communities to transition smoothly from legacy infrastructures to modernized, interconnected systems.

LUMEN's Data Mesh Framework is transformative. By promoting federated governance and progressive decentralisation of data ownership, this approach supports scalability and sustainability. It enables research communities to retain control over their own platforms and data, while benefiting from common discovery components that facilitate cross-domain discovery and alignment without centralisation.

Enhanced **AI powered data discoverability** fosters more efficient and transparent research workflows, enabling researchers to find, link, and reuse scientific resources across disciplines. This approach accelerates **interdisciplinary research** by facilitating seamless connections between various scientific fields, breaking down long-standing barriers between disciplines.

As LUMEN moves forward, the next steps will focus on the **standardization of metadata models and governance rules**, leading to the definition of the **LUMEN Data Model (D4.2)**. The architecture will be validated through **pilot implementations of connected discovery platforms**, allowing communities to test and refine their integration with the data mesh. Additionally, **progressive alignment with EOSC services** will further enhance interoperability and cross-disciplinary research collaboration. By providing a structured yet flexible framework for scientific data federation, LUMEN's data mesh ensures the long-term impact and sustainability of data discovery, standardization, and knowledge exchange across the research ecosystem.

This document defines the architectural foundations of the LUMEN data mesh, outlining the vision, guiding principles, and operational mechanisms that will structure the technical implementation across the project.

0. Definitions

This section provides a concise glossary of the core concepts and terms essential for understanding the LUMEN Data Mesh Architecture Framework. Only simplified, one-line definitions are presented here to facilitate quick reference and immediate comprehension for reviewers. Extended definitions, explanatory notes, and conceptual diagrams are available in [Annex A. Extended Glossary and Conceptual Notes](#) for those who require in-depth clarification or further contextual information.

Mesh (or Data Mesh)

Decentralised data architecture paradigm in which *data* is treated as a product, owned and governed by domain teams, integrated through a federated infrastructure and based on four foundational principles:

- Domain-oriented data ownership and architecture, covering both the structuring of data and the design of services and components enabling their exposure, governance, and interoperability
- Data as a product
- Self-serve data infrastructure as a platform
- Federated governance

Data Mesh Architecture Framework

Structured architectural model that formalises the LUMEN vision of the data mesh, by describing the conceptual layers, technical components, and federation mechanisms that enable communities to expose, discover, and govern their data products collaboratively.

Resource (or Scientific Resource)

Structured unit of scientific content that can be described, referenced, and potentially reused. Resources may include datasets, publications, software, semantic artefacts, multimedia assets, or any other formal output of scientific activity.

Data Product

FAIR, self-contained, and discoverable data asset that encapsulates *data*, *metadata* and associated governance, designed to deliver measurable value to its users by applying product thinking principles.

Data Source

Entity that specifies the components or platform through which a data product is made discoverable, by exposing its structured metadata.

Data Contract

Structured agreement between a scientific community and the LUMEN federation that specifies an association between a data product and a data source, capturing the specific conditions of exposure and federation.

Metadata

Structured information that describes, contextualises, or enables the discovery, interpretation, and reuse of a data product, including its underlying scientific resources.

Hosting

Process by which a system stores, preserves, and provides access to the content of a scientific resource in a durable and reliable manner.

Exposing

Act of making structured data product metadata accessible through standardised interfaces, in order to support discovery, referencing, and potential reuse across platforms.

Common Data Model (or LUMEN Data Model)

Data model that defines the core entities, relationships, and metadata attributes used across the federation to describe, publish, and govern data products. It acts as a shared semantic backbone enabling interoperability between communities, platforms, and services, while remaining flexible enough to support domain-specific extensions.

FAIR Principles

Set of guidelines designed to improve the management and stewardship of scientific data and related outputs, by ensuring they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

Domain Ownership

Principle whereby a designated actor assumes responsibility for the exposure, quality, and alignment of resources associated with a specific scientific community.

Decentralisation

Architecture model in which control, ownership, and data are distributed across independent entities, without reliance on any central point of coordination.

Federation (or LUMEN Federation)

Structured collaboration model among autonomous entities that retain their independence and domain ownership while adhering to a common set of principles, protocols, or standards.

Community (or Scientific Community)

Group of actors organised around a scientific domain and contributing collectively to research data publication, alignment, and governance.

Connected Communities

A transitional state in which scientific communities maintain their own infrastructures and governance but are already engaged in technical and/or

semantic exchanges, enabling early alignment, mutual visibility, and shared discovery.

Community Liaison

Designated representative of a scientific community responsible for ensuring coordination, communication, and alignment between the community and the LUMEN federation.

Technical Coordinator

Expert appointed within the federation to support technical alignment, operational coordination, and onboarding of scientific communities.

Guild (or Community Guild)

Governance body composed of formally designated representatives from participating scientific communities and technical coordinators, tasked with collectively steering the evolution, validation, and alignment processes within the LUMEN federation.

Individual

Entity representing a natural person involved in the creation, curation, or stewardship of scientific resources.

Organisation

Entity representing a structured group or institution (e.g. university, research institute, consortium) that participates in scientific activities or manages resources.

Agent

Entity (either an individual or an organisation) primarily responsible for the intellectual content or creation of a scientific resource.

Agent profile

A structured metadata record that describes the identity, affiliations, expertise areas, and contributions of an agent (individual or organisation) involved in scientific activities.

Research Literature

Scientific resource that formally communicates research findings through textual or visual content disseminated via recognised academic channels.

Dataset

Scientific resource consisting of a structured collection of data, organised in a defined format, and intended to be analysed, processed, or reused in support of scientific research.

Software

Scientific resource composed of source code, scripts, libraries, or executable programs designed to perform computational tasks or support research workflows.

Semantic Artefact

Scientific resource that provides a structured, machine-actionable and readable formalisation of a conceptualisation that enables the sharing and reuse by humans and machines. They may vary in complexity, from loose sets of terms to formal ontologies. While they are often serialised in RDF-based formats (e.g. RDF Turtle, OWL, JSON-LD), other representations (e.g. XML, CSV, JSON) may also be used, provided they support machine-actionable semantics.

Multimedia asset

Scientific resource consisting of non-textual content such as images, audio recordings, video footage, or visualisations that support or document research

Project

Structured scientific activity undertaken to address a defined research objective, typically constrained by time, funding, and institutional or collaborative frameworks.

Molecule

A structured scientific object representing a chemical or biological entity, typically identified through a name, formula, or structural representation, and used in research contexts such as molecular dynamics, structural biology, or material science.

Layer

A conceptual level within an architecture that organises related responsibilities, functions, or components into a coherent group, often corresponding to a distinct concern or role in the architecture.

Connected Communities Ecosystem

Decentralised layer of the LUMEN Data Mesh Framework, composed of connected communities that manage their own infrastructures, platforms, and governance, while progressively engaging in collaboration and alignment with the federation.

Common Discovery Infrastructure

Layer of the LUMEN Data Mesh Framework, composed of all interoperable components, platforms, and services designed to support cross-domain discovery, alignment, and access to data products across the LUMEN federation.

Federated Shared Data Governance

Layer of the LUMEN Data Mesh Framework, composed of shared roles, rules, and processes defined and enacted by autonomous communities to ensure coherence, interoperability, and trust across the federation.

Component

Functional building block that implements a specific function contributing to data discovery, exposure, or interoperability.

Service

Concrete function provided by a component and made accessible through a defined interface, enabling a specific operation on data products.

Interface

Defined point of interaction through which a platform, component, or service makes functionalities or resources and data products accessible to users or other platforms.

Protocol

Formal specification of rules and formats governing the exchange of information between platforms, components, or services.

Platform (or Portal)

Concrete configuration designed to support a specific domain, community, or use case by integrating multiple components and services into a coherent operational environment.

Catalogue

Component designed to support the discovery, access, and governance of scientific resources. It aggregates structured metadata and may integrate various roles such as describing resources (registry), hosting them (repository), or exposing them for discovery and reuse.

Core Discovery Asset

Key interoperable element of the LUMEN Common Discovery Infrastructure layer that provides essential capabilities for the discovery, alignment, or access to data products across the federation.

White-Label Discovery Platform

Reusable discovery component designed to be deployed as a platform and configured by individual communities to expose and explore data products in alignment with LUMEN federation principles.

LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (or LUMIS)

Platform and set of services designed to support the creation, validation, curation, publication, and reuse of semantic artefacts in a machine-actionable, interoperable, and FAIR-compliant manner.

Meta-Search (or Meta-Search Engine)

Component or platform that enables discovery and cross-domain querying of data products exposed by LUMEN communities.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context and motivation

Scientific research today faces increasingly complex challenges in managing, sharing, and reusing data across disciplines. Vast volumes of data are generated daily within individual scientific communities, ranging from publications and datasets to software and simulation outputs. However, much of this information remains siloed within local platforms, institutional repositories, or domain-specific infrastructures. These silos are often reinforced by heterogeneous data models, inconsistent metadata practices, and the lack of shared governance or alignment on technical standards.

While many initiatives have attempted to centralise data through large repositories or data lakes, such approaches often face significant challenges. These are not solely due to centralisation itself, but rather to shortcomings in implementation: rigid interfaces, limited documentation, inconsistent metadata, or lack of harmonised governance often make integration and reuse costly in time and effort.

Beyond these practical barriers, centralised systems tend to struggle with scalability and long-term agility. As the volume and diversity of data increase, maintaining performance, semantic consistency, and responsiveness within a monolithic architecture becomes increasingly complex. By contrast, federated and decentralized architectures distribute this responsibility across autonomous nodes, allowing communities to evolve their systems at their own pace, while collectively adhering to shared interoperability principles. This decentralised model supports greater resilience, promotes innovation at the edges, and reflects the diversity of scientific practices across domains.

As scientific problems become more interdisciplinary and dependent on collaborative knowledge, the inability to seamlessly connect data across domains increasingly limits innovation. Whether it is combining climate and health data to model the impact of pollution, or linking humanities research with linguistic corpora and AI tools, cross-domain exploration requires more than just open access: it requires interoperability, structured metadata, shared discovery mechanisms, and agreed-upon quality standards.

This is precisely the context in which LUMEN proposes to adopt a data mesh architecture as an alternative to traditional centralised data infrastructures – an approach that closely aligns with the ongoing evolution of EOSC itself, which is progressively organised as a federation of nodes following a decentralised "system of systems" model. Instead of aggregating all data into a single repository or platform, the data mesh model federates data ownership and empowers scientific communities to expose their resources as structured, discoverable, and reusable data products. Each community retains full responsibility for its data, but does so by aligning with shared interoperability rules, semantic frameworks, and federated governance mechanisms.

By shifting the paradigm from platform-centric to domain-driven data publication, LUMEN recognises the diversity of research practices while promoting cross-disciplinary data discovery and reuse. This architectural vision is anchored in the principles of FAIR data, the promotion of semantic alignment without uniformity,

and the use of data contracts to standardise access, structure, and quality requirements across the ecosystem.

To implement this vision, the LUMEN architecture is structured around three interconnected layers that together operationalise the data mesh principles across the scientific landscape:

- **Connected Communities Ecosystem:** Each community (e.g., SSH, Maths, Earth System, Molecular Dynamics) retains ownership of its scientific resources and exposes it through one or more data products, which may include discovery platforms or other domain-specific services. These data products are described and governed using data contracts, which define structure, semantics, access conditions, and quality expectations.
- **Common Discovery Infrastructure:** To support these decentralised actors, LUMEN provides a domain-agnostic set of services including a White-Label Discovery Platform, a LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics, and tools for metadata refinement and enrichment. These services enable communities to expose FAIR-compliant data, enrich their metadata semantically, and facilitate interoperability without imposing uniformity.
- **Federated Data Sharing Governance:** A collective governance layer defines global policies and guidelines for federation. This includes shared protocols, alignment with FAIR and EOSC principles, and validation of data contracts to ensure interoperability and consistency across the mesh. The governance model ensures trust, scalability, and accountability across participating communities.

In this architecture, each of these three pillars corresponds to a layer, a conceptual structure organising the logic of the mesh. The platforms and services that operate within these layers, such as the White-Label Discovery Platform or the Meta-Search Engine, are implemented as modular components, each contributing specific functions to discovery, exposure, or interoperability within the LUMEN architecture. This distinction clarifies how LUMEN structures its federated architecture: the conceptual layers define roles, responsibilities, and governance scopes, while the components implement the specific technical functions that enable discovery, exposure, and interoperability across the federation.

Together, these three layers establish the foundation of LUMEN's data mesh: a distributed, standards-driven, and semantically enriched ecosystem where communities remain autonomous yet interoperable, and where data becomes more discoverable, actionable, and reusable at scale.

By introducing a common architectural language and distributed technical foundation, LUMEN provides a concrete path for scientific communities to move from fragmented infrastructures toward a collaborative, resilient, and interoperable data ecosystem.

Figure – The data mesh enables isolated scientific communities to interconnect, share resources, and collaborate on discovery while preserving autonomy.

1.2 Scope of the document

This document is intended as a reference for all stakeholders involved in LUMEN, including technical teams, scientific communities, governance actors, and communication leads.

Specifically, it covers:

- The articulation of key architectural principles that support federation, FAIR compliance, and cross-domain interoperability.
- The description of the three main layers of the LUMEN's architecture: the Connected Communities Ecosystem, the Common Discovery Infrastructure and the Federated Data Sharing Governance
- The roles and expected behaviours of the three core discovery assets: the White-Label Discovery Platform, the LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics and the Meta-Search Engine.
- Concrete use cases and mechanisms illustrating how communities integrate into the data mesh through the definition of data products and data contracts.
- Criteria for validation, scalability principles, and interoperability with broader ecosystems such as EOSC.

It is important to note that this document does neither provide the full design nor the implementation specifications of each component, which are covered in dedicated tasks and future deliverables. Instead, it offers a unified and high-level architectural framework that serves as a common foundation and coordination guide for all contributors throughout the project.

2. Understanding the LUMEN Data Mesh

2.1 What is a data mesh?

The concept of data mesh emerged as a response to the limitations of traditional centralised data architectures, especially in large, heterogeneous, and fast-evolving ecosystems[1]. Rather than aggregating all data into a single data warehouse or monolithic platform, a data mesh promotes a decentralised approach in which data is treated as a product[2], managed directly by domain teams under shared interoperability rules.

This model contrasts with traditional data warehouses or lakes by emphasizing scalability, domain autonomy, and interconnectivity. In scientific research, characterized by vast, heterogeneous, and distributed datasets, this paradigm is gaining traction. Rather than aggregating all data into a single repository, scientific data mesh strategies envision a federated ecosystem of interconnected platforms where each community retains control over its data while enabling discoverability and reuse, aligned with the FAIR principles[3].

Such ecosystems, sometimes referred to as data commons, combine disciplinary data infrastructures with shared computational services and federated governance. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) exemplifies this approach by integrating national repositories, thematic infrastructures, and cloud services into a pan-European mesh federation¹. In Germany, the NFDI roadmap similarly aims to interlink 27 disciplinary consortia under a distributed governance model².

Comparable efforts exist worldwide (e.g., the Australian Research Data Commons and NIH's Data Commons), but Europe stands out for its coordinated continental strategy. Initiatives like EGI-ACE³ have begun deploying thematic data spaces within EOSC, which bundle FAIR datasets and web-based analysis tools to provide domain-specific research environments while leveraging a federated computing infrastructure.

Ultimately, the goal is to create an interconnected network of data platforms, each new node strengthening the collective capacity for cross-domain discovery, reuse, and collaboration. However, this distributed architecture requires shared semantic frameworks and robust governance mechanisms to prevent fragmentation and ensure interoperability.

A data mesh architecture relies on four key principles:

- Domain-oriented data ownership and architecture
- Data as a product
- Self-serve data infrastructure as a platform
- Federated computational governance

One of the key innovations of the data mesh paradigm is the concept of “data as a product”. In LUMEN, this principle is extended through the definition of governed, FAIR-compliant data products. A detailed discussion, including criteria and examples, is provided in Section 2.3.1.

LUMEN adopts and extends this data mesh paradigm to fit the reality of scientific communities. The federation model proposed by LUMEN preserves the four foundational principles, but adapts them to:

- a cross-disciplinary environment, where semantic alignment must be flexible and respectful of domain diversity,
- a community-driven governance model, balancing autonomy with shared policies,
- a need for FAIR-compliant data products, often composed of heterogeneous scientific resources (e.g. datasets, software, publications, ontologies),
- and an open, publicly funded context, where transparency, reuse, and long-term sustainability are essential.

¹ CS3MESH4EOSC. (2023). *Science Mesh project*. <https://cs3mesh4eosc.eu>

² AWI. (2022). *National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) roadmap*. <https://epic.awi.de>

³ EGI. (2023). *EGI-ACE: Advanced computing and data spaces for EOSC*. <https://www.egi.eu/project/egi-ace/>

In the LUMEN implementation, the data product is complemented by two essential concepts: the data contract and the data source. While the data product defines the content to be shared, including its structure, purpose, and associated metadata, the data contract formalises the governance, access conditions, and interoperability rules under which the product is exposed. The data source specifies the components or the platform through which the data product is made discoverable, typically via standardised protocols. This tripartite model ensures that each data product is not only reusable and FAIR-compliant, but also formally interoperable across domains, based on transparent, verifiable agreements between communities and the federation.

Although the notion of data contract is not part of the original data mesh paradigm, which emphasises decentralised ownership and product thinking, LUMEN introduces it as a necessary extension to address the challenges of cross-disciplinary scientific collaboration. In this context, data contracts provide a lightweight but explicit framework to align expectations, enable automation, and reinforce trust between data providers and consumers, while preserving the autonomy of each domain. In essence, LUMEN proposes a scientific implementation of the data mesh, rooted in the same architectural foundations but reinterpreted to serve decentralised research communities, interoperable metadata ecosystems, and progressive EOSC integration.

Figure - From scientific resources to FAIR Data Products: the role of the 3 key concepts involved in the LUMEN Data Mesh Framework

In the context of scientific research and Open Science, this approach enables communities to publish, govern, and reuse data in a way that respects their autonomy while ensuring semantic and technical interoperability across domains[6]. But this conceptual evolution is not limited to scientific contexts. In the private sector, organisations have begun to implement data mesh architectures with formalised data contracts as a cornerstone of federated governance. PayPal[32] applies this model in the financial domain, where domain-owned “data quanta” are exposed and consumed under structured contracts to ensure quality and service guarantees. In the travel sector, eDreams ODIGEO[5] leverages declarative data contracts to automate ingestion and validation pipelines across microservices. Nando’s⁴, in the retail industry, uses a dedicated internal contract service to coordinate data dependencies across autonomous business units. These operational implementations demonstrate the scalability and versatility of data contracts in diverse environments and reinforce LUMEN’s position as a research-driven adaptation of an increasingly adopted paradigm.

2.2 Federation and decentralisation in LUMEN

In a federated model, autonomous actors collaborate through shared rules and services, while certain functions (e.g. discovery, identity, governance) are coordinated at a common level. This concept of federation, as used in LUMEN, differs from political federations where autonomy may be limited by central authority. Here, autonomy is both real and operational. In a fully decentralised model, by contrast, each actor operates independently and does not rely on shared components. Even metadata exposure, governance, and resolution are entirely distributed, typically coordinated through protocol-defined consensus mechanisms rather than a central authority.

The LUMEN implementation of the data mesh adopts a federated model in which scientific communities already host and operate their own platforms and services, reflecting a real degree of decentralisation in practice. This autonomy is complemented by a set of shared components, such as the White-Label Discovery Platform and the Meta-Search Engine, which support cross-domain interoperability and collective visibility.

While shared components exist, the federation does not impose exclusivity or assignment to a single service. Communities may deploy or choose among redundant services, provided they conform to federation rules. This flexibility supports innovation, local optimisation, and, when appropriate, user-level choice between comparable tools.

4

<https://medium.nandos.dev/running-a-modern-data-platform-at-nandos-part-1-2-overview-6b66ccd35350>

LUMEN recognises that integration into the federation is not binary: communities can engage progressively as Connected Communities, by adopting shared protocols, exposing resources, or participating in semantic alignment, even before formalising their integration through data contracts.

Coordination within this model is enabled by formally appointed Community Liaisons, who represent their communities and ensure alignment between local practices and federation-wide rules. These liaisons collectively participate in the Guild, the governance body responsible for validating data contracts, defining eligibility criteria, and supporting strategic alignment.

In this sense, LUMEN does not oppose federation and decentralisation: it positions federation as a flexible and pragmatic coordination layer that enables decentralised communities to collaborate through common protocols, semantic profiles, and data contracts, while preserving their independence.

Federation in LUMEN is thus a structured and evolutive model: decentralised capabilities are already in place, but supported and enhanced by shared infrastructure, distributed governance mechanisms, and transitional states such as connectedness that reduce fragmentation and foster convergence.

Finally, to support this vision and enable interoperability at scale, LUMEN aims to build upon existing specifications, such as FAIR Data Point (FDP)[7], for metadata exposure and federation protocols, aligning with the broader FAIR ecosystem and facilitating reuse of domain-specific infrastructures.

Figure - This figure contrasts three models for organising scientific communities and services. In a centralised system, all activity is routed through a central authority, often at the cost of autonomy and scalability. In a fully decentralised approach, communities retain full independence, but lack coordination and shared visibility. LUMEN proposes a federated model: decentralised communities collaborate via shared infrastructure and governance, preserving autonomy while enabling gradual interoperability and collective alignment.

2.3 Main data mesh concepts

2.3.1 What is a data product?

In LUMEN, a data product is a governed package that encapsulates one or more scientific resources that is intentionally exposed by a community or selected for inclusion in order to be reused within the LUMEN federation.

This can mean:

- a single dataset, like field observations of plant species;
- a publication enriched with semantic annotations;
- or a curated collection, like a registry of climate models or research software tools.

A data product is defined by three key characteristics:

- It is **scoped**
 - The resource must be clearly identified. It can be:
 - a single dataset or software package,
 - a publication or a semantic artefact,
 - or a well-defined set of related resources (e.g. a curated corpus or a registry content).
- It is **exposed**
 - A data product is made accessible through a machine-actionable interface, such as an API or a metadata catalogue.
 - This exposure happens via a data source: a platform or repository that hosts or serves the resource. However, the platform itself is not the data product.
- It is **governed**
 - The resource must be accompanied by a data contract that defines its structure, semantics, update policy, access conditions, and quality expectations.
 - This data contract transforms a scientific resource into a reusable, trustable, and FAIR-aligned data product.

A data product must represent a coherent unit of scientific value: it is not defined by its granularity. What qualifies it as a data product is not its size or internal structure, but the fact that it is intentionally exposed for reuse, governed through explicit responsibilities, and described as a single, coherent unit. This unit may be a dataset, a software registry, a set of author profiles, or a collection of publications – as long as it is made accessible through a defined interface and managed under a dedicated data contract.

This means it is:

- large enough to carry standalone meaning,
- but focused enough to be intelligible, reusable, and governed as a product

It is not:

- an individual database row,
- a raw table without context,

- or an opaque file exported from a platform.

But typically, it is:

- a single publication, e.g. a monograph in open access with complete metadata and licensing,
- a standalone software package, e.g. a simulation tool deposited in a repository with versioning and documentation,
- a semantic artefact, e.g. a specific version of the SWEET ontology or a disciplinary vocabulary,
- a well-scoped dataset e.g. "all satellite observations over France in 2022",
- a curated software list,
- or an aggregated corpus with known content and purpose
- etc.

If you can ask: *"Would someone outside the source system understand what this is, reuse it, and cite it as a scientific resource?"*, then it probably has the right scope.

In short, a data product is not defined by what it is, but by how it is shared.

It is not simply data, it is data made usable, interoperable, and trustworthy within the LUMEN federation.

Why is this necessary?

This concept is central to the LUMEN data mesh because it provides a common unit of exchange across highly diverse communities, without forcing them to adopt the same tools or data models.

By treating data as a product, rather than a by-product, each community retains ownership of its content, while committing to a shared framework for interoperability and reuse.

Data products allow the federation to grow organically, with each participant contributing resources at their own pace, as long as they are exposed in a reusable and contractually defined way.

In this model, interoperability does not come from central control, but from the ability of autonomous actors to expose their data in meaningful, structured, and trustable forms.

Examples

In practice, LUMEN data products take many forms, depending on the domain and the needs of each community. For instance:

- From Earth System:
 - A harmonised set of metadata records describing georeferenced Earth System datasets, exposed as a single data product. The metadata is aggregated from multiple disciplinary and national sources, including thematic catalogs (e.g; Sextant⁵, Data terra hub catalogs⁶, RDG⁷) or

⁵ <https://sextant.ifremer.fr/>

⁶ <https://www.data-terra.org/>

⁷ <https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/>

repositories (e.g. EaSy Data⁸, Seanoe⁹, and PANGAEA¹⁰) and described using ISO 19115 or GeoDCAT standards to ensure semantic interoperability.

- From Mathematics:
 - A curated registry of mathematical software components maintained in zbMATH Open¹¹, where each software entry is treated as a data product. The metadata includes version history, authorship, persistent identifiers, and links to related publications. The registry is exposed via a disciplinary platform and made interoperable through a data contract that defines update policies and semantic alignment.
- From Molecular Dynamics:
 - A structured collection of scientific entity records describing molecules referenced in Molecular Dynamics datasets and publications. Each record includes metadata such as identifiers, provenance, links to publications, external databases, and simulation tools.
- From Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH):
 - An aggregated corpus of open-access publication metadata from GoTriple¹², combining bibliographic records, subject classifications, and persistent identifiers into a searchable FAIR dataset.

Each of these examples illustrates how communities can contribute very different kinds of resources, but all qualify as data products when they are clearly scoped, exposed through a machine-actionable interface, and governed by a data contract.

2.3.2 What is a data source?

LUMEN introduces the concept of a Data Source as a distinct architectural element: a data source specifies the components or the platform through which the data product is made discoverable and provides metadata about one or more data products through machine-actionable interfaces, while potentially applying validation, enrichment, or formatting processes that affect how the products are integrated into the mesh.

A data source is not the data product itself, nor does it always host the actual data. But in practice, it often determines:

- the metadata format (e.g. ISO 19115 or GeoDcat for Earth communities),
- the semantic alignment (e.g. use of controlled vocabularies or ontologies, findable in semantic artefact catalogues such as the EarthPortal),
- the access and licensing conditions (e.g. embargo rules or licence lists imposed by a repository),

⁸ <https://easydata.earth>

⁹ <https://www.seanoe.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

¹¹ <https://zbmath.org/>

¹² <https://gotriple.eu/>

- and even the acceptance criteria (e.g. minimal metadata quality required before publication, curation process).

Why is this necessary?

In the original Data Mesh paradigm[8], data products are the primary artefacts, autonomous, addressable, trustworthy, and reusable units that encapsulate data and its associated governance. The model assumes that each data product is published and maintained by a domain team, with a clear contract of quality and service attached to it. The notion of a data source is not formally described.

However, in real scientific infrastructures, as illustrated in Earth System Science (e.g. EaSy Data) or SSH (e.g. GoTriple), the situation is more complex: resources are often exposed through shared platforms and components (catalogues, repositories, registries) that apply their own policies for curation, formatting, metadata enrichment, and access. These systems may not produce the data, but they actively shape how it is made discoverable and reusable.

This is why in LUMEN, a data contract is not only attached to the data product itself, but also applies to the specific combination of the data product and the data source through which it is exposed.

This layered model reflects the real-world governance structures observed in platforms like EaSy Data, where communities define their own moderation, curation, and exposure policies.

Examples

The following platforms illustrate how data sources operate within the LUMEN federation:

- The GoTriple platform (SSH), exposing publication metadata through APIs and OAI-PMH endpoints
- The LUMEN white-label discovery platform for Earth System, aggregating metadata from thematic data catalogues and data repositories., with OGC-compatible services such as CSW.
- zbMATH Open (Mathematics), publishing structured metadata about mathematical document, authors or software tools
- The EarthPortal semantic artefact catalogue, exposing curated metadata of ontologies and controlled vocabularies with MOD-API¹³.

In short, data sources are the technical and policy gateways through which data products are exposed to the federation. Understanding their role is essential to managing interoperability, quality, and responsibility in a federated data mesh.

¹³ <https://github.com/FAIR-IMPACT/MOD-API>

2.3.3 What is a data contract?

In LUMEN, a data contract is a structured agreement between a scientific community and the federation that formalises the conditions under which a data product is exposed through a specific data source. It specifies how the product is documented, maintained, and made accessible, in alignment with FAIR principles and interoperability requirements. This association is central to LUMEN's federation logic, as the contract governs not only the content of the data product but also its technical and semantic exposure context. Examples of such contracts and their components are described in section 3.1.3.

A data source, such as a catalogue, repository, or discovery platform, does not merely serve the data product, it shapes how the product is discovered, interpreted, and reused. It may apply its own metadata schema, access protocols, validation steps, or exposure policies. This means that the same data product, when exposed via two different sources, may require two distinct contracts, each describing how the product is formatted, described, governed, and accessed through that source.

By capturing this binding between product and source, the data contract ensures that interoperability, access conditions, and quality expectations are clearly specified and verifiable. It transforms an abstract scientific resource into a governed, reusable unit that is not only technically accessible, but aligned with shared federation rules, regardless of where or how it is hosted.

Communities play a role in this process as actors responsible for the exposure or curation of the data product through a given source. But the contract itself is structured around the data product / data source pair, which defines the unit of federation.

The notion of a data contract is rooted in the original vision of the data mesh, which emphasized domain ownership, product thinking, and explicit commitments for usability and governance. While early definitions did not formalise contracts as standalone artefacts, LUMEN extends this vision by making the data contract a core architectural mechanism. The data contract defines not only the structure and semantics of a data product, but also the conditions under which it is federated: how it is exposed through one or more data sources, who maintains it, how often it is updated, and what level of quality or access is guaranteed.

A LUMEN data contract typically specifies:

- the schema and vocabularies used to describe the product;
- the protocols and formats for accessing the metadata;
- the update policy, including the frequency of metadata curation and mechanisms for maintaining accuracy, accessibility, and relevance over time;
- the roles and responsibilities of the involved community;
- any quality indicators (e.g. completeness, availability, documentation);
- and the data source(s) through which the product is exposed.

This structured approach ensures that each data product is not only technically accessible, but also semantically aligned and governance-aware.

Why is this necessary?

In many real-world repositories, such as EaSy Data or EarthPortal, resources are not always produced and governed by the same actor. Sometimes the data source imposes its own policies on metadata structure, access, or quality – even though the resource itself comes from an external producer.

To account for this diversity of situations, LUMEN introduces a flexible model of engagement within the contract. Each contract can reflect one or several types of relationships between the community and the data product:

Role	Description	Example
Producer	The community is responsible for hosting and governing the data product as a FAIR-aligned asset. It may or may not be the original creator of the underlying resource.	Dataset deposited and governed in EaSy Data
Enhancer	The community enriches or validates metadata for an external product.	Semantic artefacts in EarthPortal curated but not authored by Data Terra
Aggregator	The community aggregates metadata from various sources without curating the content.	A thematic collection built by harvesting external RDF endpoints
Reference	The community highlights external resources it considers relevant, with no commitment attached.	A Zenodo dataset linked for discoverability without guarantees

These roles are not exclusive: a single contract can combine, for instance, aggregation and enhancement responsibilities.

In the LUMEN Data Mesh framework, a data contract is always associated with both a data product and a data source. This reflects the fact that a product may be exposed in different ways by different platforms, each with its own constraints and guarantees.

Examples

To better understand how data contracts operate within the LUMEN federation, the following real-world examples illustrate the relationship between a data product, the

data source that exposes it, and the type of contract that governs its inclusion, whether through direct production, community curation, or external referencing.

Example 1 – Producer data contract (Mathematics)

- *Data Product*: A collection of open-access mathematical publications, including journal articles and conference proceedings, with structured metadata and links to full text (PDF and/or JATS-XML).
- *Data Source*: The Centre Mersenne platform (operational) and the forthcoming Geodesic MDML catalogue (in development), both operated by mathematics communities. These platforms expose full-text and metadata records through machine-actionable interfaces.
- *Data Contract*:
 - Type: Producer
 - The communities managing Centre Mersenne and Geodesic produce, host, and govern the full publication records. The data contract specifies their full responsibility over metadata quality, semantic structure (e.g. MathML, JATS-XML), update frequency, licensing, and long-term availability.
 - Inclusion in the LUMEN Mesh is based on this end-to-end governance and FAIR alignment, enabling discovery, reuse, and cross-domain integration of mathematical literature.

Example 2 – Enhancer data contract (Earth System)

- *Data Product*: A single, externally developed semantic vocabulary (e.g. SWEET Ontology) describing Earth System concepts.
- *Data Source*: EarthPortal, a platform curated by Data Terra, which hosts selected semantic artefacts. The platform does not harvest these from other registries, but ingests and documents them individually with controlled metadata.
- *Data Contract*:
 - Type: Enhancer
 - The community does not author the SWEET ontology, but chooses to reference, validate, and curate its metadata and documentation within EarthPortal.
 - No harvesting or batch aggregation is performed. Instead, the artefact is selected based on scientific relevance, manually reviewed, and annotated (e.g. domain, status, version, community relevance).
 - The data contract reflects this commitment, specifying the curation scope and update responsibilities – but clearly excludes any role of aggregation.

Example 3 - Aggregator + Enhancer data contract (Mathematics)

- *Data product*: a set of software metadata records that have been chosen and made richer by the community. It could be a piece of information from another catalogue.

- *Data Source*: The dedicated LUMEN Software Catalogue, which harvests metadata from external platforms and enriches it using sources such as GitHub, GitLab, and Software Heritage.
- *Data Contract*:
 - Type: Aggregator + Enhancer
 - The community behind the catalogue does not author the software nor its original metadata, but aggregates existing records (Aggregator role), and applies structured enrichment (Enhancer role), including license harmonisation, version detection, and linkage to code repositories or citation data.
 - The data contract specifies:
 - the origin of the aggregated metadata;
 - the scope and methods of enrichment;
 - the fields curated or verified;
 - and the limitations on editorial control or update guarantees.

Here this example highlights an important nuance. In this example, both the data product and the data source are indeed catalogues, but they serve distinct roles in the LUMEN framework:

- *The data product is the content: a curated set of software metadata records, selected and enriched by the community. It represents a governed, reusable unit, intentionally assembled and documented for federation and discovery.*
- *The data source is the system that exposes this content: the LUMEN Software Catalogue. It harvests, enriches, and serves the data product through machine-actionable endpoints.*

So while both take the form of catalogues, the data product refers to what is being federated, and the data source to the technical entry point used to expose it. This distinction allows us to describe how the same content could be exposed differently (e.g. enriched, restricted, versioned) depending on the source system.

Example 4 – Reference Contract (Earth System)

- *Data Product*: A CMIP6 climate simulation dataset hosted by the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF), including multi-model output for long-term climate projections.
- *Data Source*: A disciplinary catalogue managed by a LUMEN-affiliated Earth System community, which indexes selected ESGF datasets using standardised metadata (e.g. ISO 19115 or DCAT), but does not modify or enrich the original content. The catalogue provides a machine-actionable endpoint for discovery. Note: This data source is not currently implemented or planned within the LUMEN project – it is included here for illustrative purposes only. However, future integration may be explored, particularly through collaborations with infrastructures such as Climeri¹⁴ in France.
- *Data Contract*:
 - Type: Reference

¹⁴ <https://climeri-france.fr/>

- The Earth System community recognises the scientific relevance of this dataset and includes it in the LUMEN Mesh via its catalogue.
- However, the community does not curate or govern the dataset, and cannot guarantee metadata freshness, completeness, or availability of the original resource on ESGF.
- The data contract formally documents this limited role, ensuring that the resource is discoverable within the Mesh without implying editorial responsibility or stewardship.

2.4 Core architectural principles

The LUMEN data mesh proposes a decentralised and federated framework designed to support cross-domain scientific collaboration, contrasting with the usual centralised siloed approach. It enables each community to maintain autonomy over its data infrastructure, while committing to a shared set of rules that ensure interoperability, discoverability, and reuse.

At its core, the data mesh implemented in LUMEN seeks to break data silos by encouraging communities to expose their resources in a structured and interoperable way, while preserving the diversity of disciplinary practices. It promotes a shift from top-down infrastructures to a distributed ecosystem based on shared responsibility and standardised interfaces.

To ensure coherence and scalability across this ecosystem, the LUMEN implementation of the data mesh model relies **on a set of eight foundational architectural principles**. These principles are not abstract declarations: they serve as an operational reference to guide decisions, system design, and community alignment throughout the project lifecycle.

The following principles define the essential conditions for joining, contributing to, and sustaining participation in the LUMEN data mesh:

- **P1 – Domain ownership**

Data products are governed by scientific communities based on their relationship to the underlying resource and the level of responsibility they assume.

This relationship is formalised through the data contract, which captures the specific role played by each community in exposing a given data product via a designated data source. Communities may:

- Produce and host the resource (Producer role),
- Host and govern the data product directly (Producer role)
- Curate or validate the metadata of an externally hosted resource (Enhancer role),
- Aggregate metadata from external resources without editorial intervention (Aggregator role), or

- Reference an external resource without assuming governance responsibility (Reference role).

Each of these roles reflects a form of domain ownership, ensuring that the quality, contextualisation, and discoverability of data products align with community-specific practices, infrastructures, and maturity levels. This model supports diverse engagement strategies while preserving the autonomy of each community over its platforms and governance logic.

- **P2 – Federated discovery**

Resources are exposed through decentralised platforms, discoverable via shared mechanisms.

Communities may develop or adapt their own discovery platforms, provided they respect federation rules and standardised interfaces.

- **P3 – Contractual interoperability**

The exchange of metadata inside LUMEN is governed by explicit Data Contracts, which define the structure, semantics, quality, and access conditions of each Data Product..

These contracts ensure interoperability, consistency, and FAIR compliance across domains. Whether the data is open or restricted, data contracts help clarify access conditions and responsibilities in a structured and verifiable way. They also support long-term availability and alignment with FAIR principles across the federation.

- **P4 – FAIR-by-Design exposure**

All data products must be published with discoverability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability in mind.

Communities commit to adhere to the FAIR principles through metadata, protocols, and service-level expectations specified in their data contracts.

- **P5 – Autonomy with alignment**

Each community maintains technical autonomy within a shared governance framework.

The data mesh does not impose a single technology stack but requires conformance with federation eligibility criteria to ensure systemic coherence.

- **P6 – Semantic decoupling with alignment**

Semantic alignment is encouraged without enforcing ontological uniformity.

The shared LUMEN Common Data Model, to be formalised in Deliverable D4.2, will provide a flexible and extensible structure for describing data products, enabling cross-domain discovery and integration. Rather than prescribing a fixed ontology, this common data model will serve as a semantic convergence

layer, built upon existing, broadly adopted vocabularies, preferably general-purpose ones, and will support mappings from heterogeneous domain-specific semantics across the federation. Alignment is further supported by the LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics which offers tools and workflows for creating FAIR-by-design semantic artefacts, FAIRifying their existing semantic artefacts and harmonising metadata across domains through FAIR mappings with the common data model.

- **P7 – Evolutive integration**

Participation in the data mesh is progressive and non-blocking.

Legacy infrastructures and external platforms can be integrated incrementally, starting with “connected” modes of participation, via interoperable APIs, metadata catalogues, or lightweight mappings, without requiring full alignment from the outset. Through contract-based validation and iterative onboarding, participants can progressively transition toward deeper semantic and architectural integration, at their own pace and according to their technical maturity.

- **P8 – Distributed governance**

Governance is shared among community representatives through a federated layer.

Policies, validation criteria, and evolution paths are defined collectively to preserve a balance between local needs and global coherence. This is operationalised through thematic guilds, which bring together technical experts and community liaisons designated representatives who act as bridges between their communities and the federation. Guilds serve as the primary spaces for coordinating shared rules, semantic alignment, and implementation practices, ensuring that both transversal requirements and domain-specific priorities are taken into account.

Together, these eight principles define the operating logic of the LUMEN data mesh, providing a shared foundation for all contributors to align their practices, tools, and governance approaches while preserving disciplinary autonomy and fostering cross-domain collaboration.

LUMEN's architectural principles are in line with emerging recommendations such as the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) defined by the WorldFAIR project[9], which promotes community autonomy combined with aligned, domain-neutral interoperability standards.

2.5 Main architectural layers

The LUMEN data mesh is structured around a three-layer architectural framework, each layer fulfilling a specific role in supporting decentralised data publication, cross-domain discovery, and federated governance. **This layered design ensures**

alignment with the core principles of LUMEN (P1–P8), while providing a scalable and interoperable infrastructure to serve diverse communities and disciplines.

Figure – Structural overview of the LUMEN data mesh architecture and its components

Connected Communities Ecosystem

The Connected Communities Ecosystem constitutes the first layer of the LUMEN Data Mesh architecture. It is decentralised by design and reflects the foundational principle of domain-oriented ownership: each scientific community retains control over its own platforms, data practices, and governance models, while progressively aligning with the federation's interoperability framework.

This layer is not composed of infrastructure alone, it is composed of communities themselves: disciplinary teams, national infrastructures, or institutional actors who organise their contributions around scientific missions, not around imposed central services. Each community brings its own levels of maturity, technical capacity, and engagement, from well-established data platforms to emerging initiatives exploring federation for the first time.

To support this diversity, LUMEN does not impose a one-size-fits-all integration model. Instead, it provides a flexible yet structured framework that enables convergence through shared protocols, standardised interfaces, and federated agreements. Communities are free to choose how and when they participate but once they do, they commit to publishing reusable scientific resources under clearly defined technical and governance conditions.

To operationalise this layer, each community must engage in a concrete process involving the three foundational concepts:

- It must identify and scope one or more scientific resources, whether datasets, software tools, publications, or semantic artefacts, that it deems reusable beyond its own domain, and qualify them as data products.
- It must then expose these data products through a selected data source that complies with federation protocols and makes metadata machine-actionable. This source may be managed locally, shared across communities, or provided by a third party.
- Finally, it must formalise a data contract that specifies the technical and governance conditions of exposure, structure, semantics, access, frequency, and roles, based on the community's actual level of responsibility.

This process does not require full alignment from the outset. A community may start by referencing external resources with minimal curation, and progressively evolve toward deeper integration, defining richer metadata, harmonising vocabularies, and improving update guarantees. In LUMEN, the concept of a connected community captures a transitional state: a stage where technical collaboration, visibility, and protocol adoption are already in place, even if formal integration through data contracts is not yet complete. This reflects LUMEN's pragmatic and inclusive approach to federation, enabling communities to engage at their own pace while progressively aligning with shared architectural principles.

This architectural layer gives concrete form to several of LUMEN's key principles. First, it ensures *P1 – Domain Ownership*, by allowing each community to define its own roles and responsibilities with respect to the data products it contributes –

whether as producers, enhancers, aggregators, or reference actors. Second, it implements *P5 – Autonomy with Alignment*, as communities retain full control over their technologies and governance while adhering to federation rules. Finally, it operationalises *P7 – Evolutive Integration*, enabling communities to join the Mesh progressively, starting with light metadata exposure and deepening their integration over time through contractual commitments and shared standards.

Common Discovery Infrastructure

The Common Discovery Infrastructure forms the intermediate layer of the LUMEN Data Mesh architecture. This layer is composed of all interoperable services and tools designed to support cross-domain discovery, semantic alignment, and shared access to scientific resources exposed by connected communities.

Unlike the decentralised infrastructures managed by individual communities, these components operate at the federation level. They constitute a common interface layer that interconnects the diverse platforms, formats, and metadata vocabularies of the LUMEN ecosystem. Their purpose is to translate community-level heterogeneity into system-wide coherence – enabling data products to be found, understood, and reused beyond their original disciplinary context.

In practice, this layer includes:

- The 3 LUMEN core discovery assets:
 - The White-label discovery platform, adapted and deployed by participating communities to support local exploration while remaining interoperable with the federation;
 - The LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (LUMIS), which provides tools and workflows for creating, managing and aligning semantic artefacts across domains;
 - The Meta-Search Engine, which enables federated querying and cross-platform navigation;
- As well as other transversal services such as metrics dashboards, recommendation systems, or chatbots that enrich the discovery experience and ensure alignment with FAIR principles.

By design, these components are domain-agnostic: they are configurable and reusable across scientific areas, while supporting domain-specific extensions. They support a two-way flow:

- They ingest metadata and semantic artefacts from connected community infrastructures
- They expose harmonised content and shared services back to the communities and to the broader research ecosystem

These shared components must operate within an infrastructure capable of sustaining distributed growth, interoperability, and long-term resilience. Their effectiveness depends not only on their design, but on the ability of each community to deploy, scale, and maintain them autonomously, while ensuring coherence across

the federation. To that end, LUMEN promotes an architecture that balances central coordination with decentralised deployment, enabling shared services to be progressively adopted, customised, and rehosted by individual communities. This approach ensures that discovery services remain both technically robust and aligned with the diversity of community needs, making the federation sustainable by design.

This layer ensures that the federation is not merely a set of interoperable nodes, but a genuinely integrated discovery environment, anchored in shared technical infrastructure. It operationalises several key principles of the LUMEN data mesh:

- *P2 - Federated discovery*, by enabling decentralised but interoperable access to data products
- *P4 - FAIR-by-design exposure*, through shared pipelines for metadata refinement and semantic enrichment
- *P6 - Semantic decoupling with alignment*, by supporting flexible mappings between diverse community vocabularies and shared semantic references
- *P7 - Evolutive integration*, by allowing legacy systems and partial contributions to participate through modular and progressive onboarding

Federated Data Sharing Governance

The Federated Shared Data Governance constitutes the third layer of the LUMEN Data Mesh architecture. It provides the formal structure through which diverse scientific communities collectively define, validate, and evolve the rules of engagement across the federation – without relying on centralised authority. This governance layer ensures that interoperability, quality, and trust can be maintained as the ecosystem grows in scope, complexity, and disciplinary diversity.

Unlike classical governance models that impose top-down control, LUMEN's approach is federated by design. Communities retain sovereignty over their infrastructures and practices, but agree to a set of shared rules and validation procedures, expressed in technical and organisational terms, to participate in the mesh. This enables decentralised alignment: distributed contributions that interoperate coherently without requiring uniformity.

In practical terms, this layer operates through a set of roles, processes, and collective bodies:

- Community liaisons act as designated representatives of each scientific domain. They serve as contact points between their community and the federation, facilitating contract negotiation, onboarding, and alignment of local practices with shared governance expectations.
- Guilds, or governance circles, bring together these liaisons alongside technical coordinators from the project. Each guild is responsible for steering the validation of data contracts, negotiating eligibility criteria, aligning practices with EOSC frameworks, and monitoring the evolution of shared components.
- Federated governance capabilities in LUMEN encompass the progressive articulation of shared rules, processes, and expectations in several key areas:

- Data contracts, which formalise the conditions under which data products are exposed, maintained, and made interoperable;
- Data quality, including shared indicators and validation principles to support metadata coherence and FAIR alignment
- Access and privacy policies, addressing licensing, reuse conditions, and the handling of sensitive or restricted resources;
- EOSC-by-design guidelines, ensuring compatibility with EOSC standards for components intended to be integrated into the broader ecosystem – whether via the EOSC EU Node or through thematic or national Nodes, depending on the service scope and maturity.

This governance model is both operational and extensible: it provides a basis for real-time onboarding, continuous improvement of shared services, and long-term sustainability of the federation. It also supports the gradual formalisation of what may begin as informal collaborations, turning connected communities into fully federated contributors.

Ultimately, this layer enables the federation to scale responsibly. It does so by ensuring that participation is not only technically possible, but also governed by transparent, verifiable, and collectively endorsed agreements. This reflects and operationalises several key LUMEN principles:

- P1 – Domain ownership, by recognising that each community retains decision-making over its own resources.
- P3 – Contractual interoperability, by ensuring that every federated data product is governed by a shared agreement.
- P5 – Autonomy with alignment, by allowing communities to participate on their own terms within a shared framework.
- P7 – Evolutive integration, by supporting progressive onboarding, flexible responsibility models, and scalable validation.
- P8 – Distributed governance, by relying on structured but inclusive processes that preserve trust and mutual accountability across the federation.

Note on implementation status:

The governance model presented reflects the current architectural vision of the LUMEN federation. It outlines the roles, processes, and capabilities required to support decentralised interoperability and shared accountability. However, this model remains provisional at this stage. Its detailed specification, including decision-making procedures, validation workflows, and policy implementation mechanisms, will be formalised and operationalised under **Task 7.4: LUMEN Governance model development and EOSC integration**, in close collaboration with all involved Work Packages. In particular, **Task 5.1: Contributions to the EOSC Federation**, which explores integration pathways with EOSC Core services (e.g. AAI, PID, long-term preservation, helpdesk, monitoring), will inform the design of participation models and significantly influence the shaping of the federation governance. This phased approach ensures coherence across governance, technical

development, and community engagement, while leaving space for iterative refinement based on real-world feedback.

3. Implementing the LUMEN Data Mesh

3.1 Connected Communities Ecosystem

This section describes how communities participate in the LUMEN federation by operationalising its first architectural layer: the Connected Communities Ecosystem. It introduces the core concepts that enable communities to expose and share scientific resources in a federated way, namely, data products, data sources, and data contracts.

3.1.1 Exposing the data products

To be reused across scientific domains, data products must first be made discoverable, understandable, and trustworthy – not only within their original context, but across a diverse ecosystem of users, platforms, and services. In LUMEN, this means much more than simply publishing files or datasets online.

A data product only becomes truly reusable when its structure, meaning, and governance context are made explicit through high-quality, machine-actionable metadata.

More precisely, data product metadata are expected to describe the following key elements, each of which plays a specific role in enabling discovery, interpretation, and reuse across the federation:

- **The type of resource(s)** the product contains. For instance, a data product may consist of:
 - a collection of datasets from climate observatories (e.g. temperature time series),
 - an open-access publication in philosophy harvested from GoTriple,
 - or a set of research software packages maintained by the mathematics community through zbMATH Open.
- **The metadata schema** used to describe the internal resources related to the data product. This refers to the structured vocabulary and property set used to document the resources. Examples include:
 - the TRIPLE ontology¹⁵ for multilingual publication records in SSH,
 - DataCite for repository-based datasets with persistent identifiers[10],
 - SPAR Ontologies¹⁶, i.e. a suite of orthogonal and complementary modules for the creation of comprehensive machine-readable metadata for every aspect of semantic publishing and referencing: document description, bibliographic resource identifiers, types of citations and related contexts, bibliographic references, document parts and status, agents' roles and contributions, bibliometric data and workflow processes.
 - CodeMeta for describing software with versioning and dependencies [11],

¹⁵ <https://gotriple.eu/ontology/triple>

¹⁶ <http://www.sparontologies.net>

- The MOD Ontology¹⁷, used for describing semantic artefacts such as thesauri, vocabularies, and ontologies, including their scope, type, governance, and usage context across disciplines.
- The SemanticScience Integrated Ontology (SIO) can also be used to describe the metadata record of a molecule as a scientific object[35]. SIO offers a generic, semantically rich framework to capture identifiers, provenance, usage context, and roles, making it more suitable for exposing molecules as data products in knowledge graphs.
- or SKG-IF, developed within the Research Data Alliance¹⁸ and EOSC initiatives like GraspOS¹⁹, used to express relations between scientific entities across domains (e.g. linking authors, datasets, and software tools).
- **The internal data structure and format** of the content. This refers to how the content of the data product is organised and serialised. In many cases, a single data product may expose multiple formats or structural patterns, depending on its complexity or intended uses. For example:
 - a CSV file containing tabular biodiversity observations (e.g. one row per species occurrence),
 - a JSON API providing nested author–publication–project relationships from a SSH platform,
 - or a Turtle/JSON-LD RDF graph representing molecules and their properties extracted from simulation datasets in molecular dynamics.
- **The governance and operational context** of the data product. This includes the practical conditions of access and maintenance. For example:
 - an OAI-PMH endpoint exposing the product from a disciplinary catalogue,
 - an update policy specifying weekly metadata synchronisation with external sources (e.g. GitHub, ORCID),
 - a Creative Commons licence (e.g. CC-BY 4.0 and CC0 1.0) applied to all metadata records,
 - and a formal data contract signed by the Earth System community, which assumes responsibility for both aggregating metadata from external sources (Aggregator role) and enriching it through validation or contextual annotation (Enhancer role); this contract defines how metadata is harvested, curated, and exposed via the data source, including update frequency, scope of enrichment, and quality expectations.

These metadata provide the semantic and operational envelope through which the data product can be discovered, cited, retrieved, and integrated, consistently and reliably, across the LUMEN federation.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/FAIR-IMPACT/MOD>

¹⁸

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/scientific-knowledge-graphs-interoperability-framework-skg-if-wg/activity/>

¹⁹ <https://graspos.eu/>

To ensure interoperability at scale, all data product metadata must be expressed in machine-actionable formats, based on recognised standards. Several initiatives have emerged in recent years to support the description of data products in data mesh architectures. These initiatives focus on defining what constitutes a data product and how it should be documented for discovery, reuse, and governance. Notable examples include:

- Data Product Descriptor Specification (DPDS) – an open specification that defines a data product as a document (typically in JSON or YAML) describing its technical components, data interfaces, and infrastructure. DPDS was developed as part of the Open Data Mesh initiative to facilitate internal alignment within organisations[12].
- Data Product Canvas – a conceptual design tool that helps teams define the scope, consumers, sources, and value proposition of a data product. It is intended as a strategic planning framework rather than a machine-actionable metadata format[13].
- Open Data Product Specification (ODPS) – an emerging community-driven effort to standardise the metadata of published data products, including discovery, versioning, and quality attributes[14].

While these initiatives provide useful foundations, none has reached universal adoption. Most focus on internal documentation and governance within a single organisation or platform. As such, they offer limited support for open, cross-platform interoperability, which is a core requirement in LUMEN’s federated model.

This is not only a matter of interoperability: conceptually, these initiatives rarely provide an adequate abstraction for what LUMEN defines as a data product, that is, a governed collection of heterogeneous research artefacts (e.g. datasets, software, publications), exposed through a shared metadata envelope and linked to a data contract.

Several existing frameworks are currently being analysed within this design space:

- DCAT[15], a W3C standard widely used for open data portals, offers a well-established RDF-based vocabulary to describe datasets, distributions, access points, and licences. It is robust, widely adopted, and interoperable. However, its conceptual model is focused on unitary datasets. It does not natively support hybrid products containing multiple resource types (e.g. a publication and a software package), nor does it capture internal metadata schemas or governance logics. Using `dc:Dataset` as a generic wrapper may obscure the semantic diversity of the content and blur distinctions critical to both reuse and compliance.
- SKG-IF[33], developed under the Research Data Alliance and EOSC initiatives like GraspOS, enables rich graph-based representations of scientific entities and their relations (e.g. datasets, authors, tools, institutions). Its core abstraction is the Research Product, which is granular and semantically expressive. However, SKG-IF currently focuses on atomic-level resources rather than composite products. It lacks an explicit construct for describing

curated collections of artefacts under shared governance, a key feature of LUMEN data products. Nevertheless, its underlying model offers a promising foundation for future extensions, and ongoing discussions within the community suggest that SKG-IF could be enriched to support federated, contract-based collections with explicit lifecycle, scope, and governance metadata.

- RO-Crate[34] provides a lightweight, JSON-LD-based approach for packaging research artefacts together with structured metadata and contextual provenance. It supports heterogeneous content and is increasingly used in research data management workflows. Yet, RO-Crate does not include formalised governance constructs, nor mechanisms for aligning product-level exposure with contracts, roles, or federation-level expectations.

These and other models are being explored within an open design space, with comparative evaluation and alignment to LUMEN's needs to be formalised as part of Deliverable D4.2.

3.1.2 Connecting the data sources

In LUMEN, a data source refers to any component that provides structured metadata describing scientific resources linked to a data product. These components may include repositories, catalogues, registries, or be part of discovery platforms. What matters is not their type, but their capacity to make scientific content visible, accessible, and reusable through structured, machine-actionable interfaces.

Connecting these heterogeneous components into a coherent federation is at the heart of LUMEN's architecture. This connection does not rely on a one-size-fits-all pipeline. Instead, it follows a flexible and progressive logic, adapted to the technical maturity, existing infrastructure, and strategic choices of each community.

Connecting through services and interfaces

To participate as a governed and discoverable node in the LUMEN mesh, a data source **must satisfy 3 core interoperability conditions**, corresponding to:

1. the structural exposure of its resource metadata via accessible endpoints,
2. the use of a compatible or transformable exchange format, and
3. a minimum level of semantic alignment with the LUMEN Data Model.

These conditions do not require architectural overhaul or adherence to a fixed platform, they define a minimum viable alignment that allows each system to plug into the federation while maintaining its autonomy.

Condition 1: Structural exposure of resource metadata

The data source must expose the resource metadata describing the scientific objects it hosts (e.g. datasets, software, publications). This exposure must take the form of a machine-actionable endpoint, such as an API or protocol interface, that allows external systems to query or harvest metadata.

Examples include:

- a REST API delivering JSON records describing datasets,
- an OAI-PMH endpoint exposing metadata about publications in Dublin Core,
- a SPARQL endpoint allowing access to RDF triples about software entities.
- an OGC API (e.g. OGC API - Features or OGC API - Records) used by geoscience communities to expose standardised metadata and spatial data services.

The key requirement is that these metadata are accessible and linked to specific data products exposed within the federation.

Condition 2: Format compatibility through transformable serialization

The metadata exposed must be provided in a format that can be parsed and interpreted by LUMEN's federation services.

LUMEN defines **JSON-LD as the preferred serialization format**, due to its alignment with linked data principles and its compatibility with semantic enrichment tools (e.g., the Meta-Search Engine or Metadata Wranglers).

However, other formats such as XML, CSV, or flat JSON are accepted as long as they can be reliably transformed into federation-compatible structures using the Common Discovery Infrastructure. The goal is not to enforce a standard, but to ensure transformability and consistency of representation.

Condition 3: Semantic alignment through declarable mappings to the LUMEN Data Model

Beyond format compatibility, a data source must make its semantic model interpretable by the federation. This does not mean replacing local vocabularies – instead, it requires that the mappings between local schemas and the federation's shared concepts be known, declared, and machine-actionable.

To facilitate this semantic alignment across heterogeneous metadata schemas, LUMEN introduces a common data model that acts as a semantic convergence layer: the LUMEN Data Model. Rather than prescribing a fixed ontology or replacing local vocabularies, the common data model provides a pivot structure that enables mappings between community-specific schemas and federation-level concepts. It serves as a reference for interpreting resource metadata consistently across domains, and for enabling cross-source discovery and aggregation.

For example, a data source may indicate that its local property `creator_name` corresponds to the generic `author` property in the common data model, which, in turn, is aligned with reference vocabularies such as schema.org[16] or SKG-IF (which supports the expression of semantic relations between scientific entities across

domains, and is developed within the Research Data Alliance²⁰ and EOSC initiatives like GraspOS²¹).

This allows shared services such as the Meta-Search Engine to understand and harmonise metadata fields that would otherwise remain isolated.

The common data model will be formally specified in Deliverable D4.2, and progressively adopted by federated components to ensure semantic interoperability without enforcing uniformity. Its use allows each data source to remain autonomous while becoming interoperable, not through strict conformity, but through transparent and documented alignment.

By enabling integration through clearly defined conditions, interface exposure, format compatibility, and semantic alignment – LUMEN offers a flexible yet robust pathway to federation. This model supports inclusivity without sacrificing coherence: each community retains full control over its infrastructure and metadata practices (Principle P1 – domain ownership), while participating in a shared ecosystem governed by explicit, verifiable commitments (Principle P3 – contractual interoperability).

Crucially, this alignment does not impose uniformity. Communities remain free to use their own semantic models, as long as their mappings to the common data model are declared and accessible. This reflects Principle P6 – semantic decoupling with alignment, ensuring that interoperability is achieved through convergence, not enforcement.

Connecting a data source is therefore not a one-off event, but a progressive federation journey. It begins with structural exposure, continues through syntactic transformation, and matures through semantic alignment and shared governance. This incremental approach ensures long-term sustainability, accommodates diverse practices, and builds mutual trust across the federation.

3.1.3 Formalising the data contracts

In the LUMEN Data Mesh, a data contract formalises the conditions under which a data product is exposed through a specific data source. This contract captures not only descriptive metadata, but the full governance, access, and interoperability logic associated with a federated exposure. It ensures that each data product is not only visible in the Mesh, but also governed under clear, verifiable, and machine-readable terms.

Critically, a data contract always refers to a pairing between:

- a data product – a scientific resource or structured collection intentionally selected for reuse,

²⁰

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/scientific-knowledge-graphs-interoperability-framework-skg-if-wg/activity/>

²¹ <https://graspos.eu/>

- and a data source – the component through which this product is exposed (e.g. catalogue, repository, discovery interface).

Even if the underlying resource is identical, each exposure may differ: one platform may enrich metadata with controlled vocabularies, another may enforce different access conditions or update policies. In LUMEN, each such exposure is governed by its own contract – reflecting the precise context of federation.

To formalise these contracts in a consistent and scalable way, LUMEN conducted a review of existing standards. The evaluation focused on key criteria:

- Openness (community-driven governance and licensing)
- Technical expressiveness (ability to encode metadata, policy, and structure)
- Machine-readability (support for automation and validation)
- Transparency (clarity for both humans and machines)
- Suitability for a distributed, interdisciplinary scientific ecosystem

Four initiatives were analysed:

- Open Data Contract Standard (ODCS)²²: a modular, YAML-based specification developed under the Linux Foundation. Originally created for data mesh environments, ODCS combines machine- and human-readability, a focus on governance and service-level attributes, and growing adoption in public-sector and research infrastructures.
- Data Contract Specification (DCS)²³: emerging from enterprise DevOps practices (e.g. Zalando, JPMorgan), DCS offers detailed technical tooling for platform-centric data contracts, but lacks institutional governance and alignment with open science practices.
- Open Data Product Specification (DPDS)²⁴: proposed by ThoughtWorks, DPDS structures data product documentation (e.g. lineage, ownership, quality), but does not define exposure or contract-level policies, making it less suitable for federated governance.
- International Data Spaces (IDSA) / GAIA-X²⁵: strongly policy-oriented frameworks promoted by European institutions, offering comprehensive governance models for sovereign data exchange. While promising for long-term convergence, they introduce complexity that may hinder lightweight adoption in scientific settings.

After this review, **LUMEN selected ODCS as the foundational model for implementing data contracts** across the mesh. ODCS provides a balanced combination of:

- expressiveness (clear structure, support for schema definitions, lifecycle rules),
- pragmatism

²² <https://bitol-io.github.io/open-data-contract-standard/>

²³ <https://github.com/datacontract/datacontract-specification>

²⁴ <https://github.com/Open-Data-Product-Initiative/v3.1>

²⁵ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-ram-5-working-draft>

- and governance transparency, allowing both human oversight and machine enforcement.

More than a static metadata format, ODCS enables LUMEN to encode, validate, automate, and version the contractual terms that define how each data product is exposed within the federation. It functions as the operational interface between disciplinary infrastructures and the federation layer: by expressing not just what is shared, but how and under what guarantees, ODCS turns federation from a declarative promise into an enforceable framework.

Each ODCS-based data contract describes how a data product is structured, maintained, and shared. This formalisation is essential for LUMEN to support federation across diverse communities. The key elements include:

- Structure and schema
 - Each data contract clearly defines how the data is organised – field names, data types, allowed values, formats (e.g. ISO dates, vocabularies).
 - This makes metadata interoperability explicit and verifiable, rather than based on assumptions. It supports automated search, validation, and even integration.
- Ownership and responsibilities
 - The data contract states who produces, curates, and maintains the data.
 - This ensures accountability and helps identify who to contact when changes or support are needed.
- Update and retention policies
 - It specifies how often the data is updated and how long it is kept.
 - This helps users assess whether the data is fresh and decide how to integrate it (e.g. static copy or live sync).
- Service-level expectations
 - ODCS can include availability, performance, and reliability indicators.
 - This allows LUMEN to distinguish between “best effort” and guaranteed data services.
 - In this context, LUMEN may draw upon existing guidelines for Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) developed by EOSC projects[17]. These instruments help clarify roles, expectations, and escalation paths between data providers, platform operators, and the federation. They may be particularly useful for formalising governance in multi-stakeholder contexts or when aligning with EOSC onboarding requirements.
- Licensing and access
 - The contract also documents legal aspects – licences, usage conditions, embargoes.
 - This enables discovery tools to show what can be accessed, reused, or restricted.
- Other useful fields:
 - Versioning and changelogs, to track the evolution of the product

- Links to related datasets or projects, to enrich context
- Validation rules, to allow automatic checks before onboarding

To support both readability and automation, LUMEN data contracts are authored in YAML, a lightweight and human-readable format widely used in software engineering and data governance. YAML makes it easy for communities to collaboratively edit, version, and validate contracts. Beyond readability, the structured nature of YAML allows for seamless transformation into JSON or JSON-LD, enabling integration with semantic web technologies and FAIR-compliant infrastructures. This dual compatibility, human-friendly editing and machine-actionable deployment, ensures that LUMEN contracts can operate across technical layers, from community-driven authoring environments to automated CI/CD pipelines and metadata registries.

Together, these contracts make each data product easier to understand, reuse, and connect, both for humans and machines.

Example 1 – Producer data contract (Mathematics)

```

id: contract-math-pubs-centre-mersenne
name: Mathematical Publications – Centre Mersenne and Geodesic
version: 1.0.0
type: producer
dataProduct:
  id: math-publications
  title: Open Access Mathematical Publications
  description: >
    A curated collection of open-access mathematical publications, including
journal
  articles and conference proceedings, with structured metadata and links to
full text
  in PDF and JATS-XML formats.
  resourceType: publicationCollection
  formats:
    - application/pdf
    - application/jats+xml
    - application/mathml+xml
  keywords:
    - Mathematics
    - Scientific Publications
    - JATS
    - Open Access
    - Scholarly Communication
  license: https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
  version: continuous
dataSource:
  - id: centre-mersenne
    title: Centre Mersenne
    curator: Mathdoc / CNRS
    endpoint: https://www.centre-mersenne.org/api/
    protocol: OAI-PMH
  - id: geodesic-mdml
    title: Geodesic MDML Catalogue
    curator: Geodesic Initiative

```



```

    endpoint: https://geodesic.math/api/
    protocol: REST+JSON
    status: in-development
  roles:
    - actor: Centre Mersenne team
      role: producer
      responsibilities:
        - Metadata production
        - Full-text hosting
        - Semantic structuring (JATS-XML, MathML)
        - Update and quality assurance
    - actor: Geodesic MDML team
      role: producer
      responsibilities:
        - Metadata ingestion
        - Long-term preservation planning
        - API development and exposure
  updatePolicy:
    frequency: monthly
    retentionPolicy: indefinite
    versioning: supported
    metadataValidation: automated + human review
  quality:
    semanticStructure: JATS-XML compliant
    metadataCompleteness: high
    accessConsistency: guaranteed
  access:
    visibility: public
    downloadAllowed: true
    usagePolicy: open-access / citation-required
  notes:
    - >
      This producer contract reflects full end-to-end governance by the
      mathematics
      community, covering metadata, full-text formats, quality, and platform
      availability.
    - >
      The data product is eligible for federation in LUMEN based on strong FAIR
      alignment
      and machine-actionable exposure.

```

This contract describes a curated collection of open-access mathematical publications, including journal articles and conference proceedings. The data product is fully produced, maintained, and governed by the mathematics community through two platforms: Centre Mersenne and the forthcoming Geodesic MDML catalogue. Both data sources provide structured metadata and full-text access via machine-actionable interfaces.

Example 2 – Enhancer data contract (Earth System)

```

id: contract-earthportal-sweet-enhancer
name: SWEET Ontology Reference in EarthPortal
version: 1.0.0

```



```

type: enhancer
dataProduct:
  id: sweet-ontology
  title: SWEET Ontology
  description: >
    A semantic vocabulary describing Earth System concepts. Maintained
externally,
    and referenced within EarthPortal by the Earth System community.
  resourceType: semanticVocabulary
  externalMaintainer: https://sweetontology.net
  keywords:
    - Earth System
    - Semantic Web
    - SWEET
    - Controlled Vocabulary
  license: https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
  version: 3.5
dataSource:
  id: earthportal
  title: EarthPortal - Semantic Artefacts Catalogue
  curator: CNRS/Data Terra
  endpoint: https://data.earthportal.eu/ontologies/SWEET/latest_submission
  protocol: html+metadata
  harvestingPolicy: none
  ingestion: manual
roles:
  - actor: Earth System Community
    role: enhancer
    responsibilities:
      - Metadata validation
      - Scientific curation
      - Automatic update upon new release
updatePolicy:
  frequency: irregular
  trigger: external release monitored
  curatorCheck: required
quality:
  metadataCompleteness: high
  validationStatus: curated
  communityRelevance: endorsed
access:
  visibility: public
  usagePolicy: reference-only
  downloadAllowed: true
notes:
  - >
    The SWEET ontology is not aggregated or transformed. It is manually reviewed
    and selectively referenced in EarthPortal for reuse and alignment in Earth
    System research.
  - >
    This contract formalises the enhancer role of the community without
    asserting authorship
    or redistribution rights over the ontology itself.

```

This contract formalises the inclusion of the SWEET Ontology, an externally maintained semantic vocabulary describing Earth System concepts. The data

product is not authored by the community but is selectively referenced, curated, and documented through EarthPortal, a semantic artefact catalogue operated by CNRS/Data Terra. The community takes on an enhancer role, focusing on metadata quality and relevance rather than content ownership.

While ODCS is fully suited to LUMEN's short- and medium-term requirements, particularly for lightweight, modular, and scalable adoption, it does not exclude long-term convergence with the broader European data space landscape. Frameworks such as IDSA²⁶, GAIA-X²⁷, and the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC)²⁸ define architectural and policy-level standards for sovereign data exchange across sectors. These initiatives offer valuable models for policy enforcement, trust frameworks, and cross-sector interoperability, dimensions where ODCS deliberately remains minimal by design.

Rather than seeing these approaches as mutually exclusive, LUMEN adopts a strategy of complementarity. ODCS provides a pragmatic and enforceable schema for community-level data contracts, enabling rapid adoption, human validation, and automation. In parallel, LUMEN remains attentive to the evolution of European and global data interoperability standards, and anticipates potential mappings between ODCS and more formal governance structures, such as IDSA usage policies, identity models, or EOSC integration interfaces.

This dual positioning allows LUMEN to combine operational efficiency with long-term interoperability readiness. It ensures that the Mesh remains agile enough to accommodate scientific diversity, while progressively aligning with strategic European frameworks as needed.

Within this perspective, further alignment with semantic and FAIR-oriented frameworks is actively considered. Given its native YAML structure and modularity, ODCS could be complemented by LinkML profiles²⁹, enabling schema-based validation, automatic documentation, and RDF conversion for integration into Linked Data infrastructures. Moreover, several ODCS fields map directly to elements of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs)³⁰, providing a basis for declarative alignment with FAIR principles and allowing communities to describe not only what is exposed, but how it meets transparency, reusability, and governance expectations. In domains requiring richer data provenance and transformation semantics, such as the social sciences, further convergence with models like DDI-CDI³¹ could also be explored. These integrations would not replace ODCS, but extend its expressiveness and compatibility, ensuring that LUMEN contracts remain interoperable across technical layers, disciplines, and policy ecosystems.

²⁶ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/offers/reference-architecture/>

²⁷ <https://gaia-x.eu/gaia-x-framework/>

²⁸ <https://dssc.eu/>

²⁹ <https://linkml.io/>

³⁰ <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

³¹ <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-cdi>

Through this approach, LUMEN ensures that every federated data product is not only technically compatible but also aligned with clear expectations of quality, governance, and interoperability, laying the groundwork for a scalable and resilient federation model.

A formal specification of the LUMEN ODCS data contract schema, including its additional properties and mappings to external standards, will be provided in Deliverable D4.2 (LUMEN Data Model Specification).

3.2 Common Discovery Infrastructure

To support the exposure, connection, and governance of data products across communities, LUMEN provides a set of shared discovery components. These common services form the backbone of the federation's infrastructure, enabling consistent indexing, semantic enrichment, and user-facing exploration of data products. The following subsections present each of these components in turn.

3.2.1 *The White-Label Discovery Platform*

Discovery platforms are crucial at every stage of the research process: they offer researchers easy access to previous studies, upon which to build their work. Creating thematic discovery platforms is essential to streamline research workflows, as this way scholars do not retrieve plenty of unrelated results— an experience researchers regularly have by making searches on huge but general scientific indexes like Google Scholar or OpenALEX. At the same time it is essential to guarantee the reliability of the content provided: so the choice of sources to index is a fundamental aspect in the management of a discovery platform.

Starting from all these motivations, the GoTriple multilingual discovery platform³² for the Social Sciences and Humanities has been developed through the TRIPLE research project. TRIPLE ran from 2019 to 2023: after that, GoTriple development has continued in other research initiatives like the ATRIUM and FASCA projects.

GoTriple.eu went live for the first time in 2021: it provides a central access point that allows users to explore, find, access and reuse materials such as articles, datasets, project descriptions and author profiles at European scale. At the time of writing, after four and a half years in operation, the platform indexes over 19 million documents, 25,000 projects and 22 million author profiles.

GoTriple proved to be an effective discovery platform in the field, with an ever-increasing number of visits (an average of about 20,000 unique visitors per month), and a growing user base (590 registered users at the time of writing).

GoTriple's software components can therefore be used as the basis upon which the White-Label Discovery Platform in LUMEN will be implemented: they will be refactored to create a domain-agnostic solution, enabling advanced discovery

³² <https://gotriple.eu/>

experiences for any scientific community. This reuse strategy aligns directly with *Principle P2 – Federated discovery*, which promotes the development or adaptation of decentralised platforms, provided they expose interoperable interfaces for search and access. New features will be added, together with the support for new kinds of content (software code, semantic artefacts, multimedia, etc.).

This approach reflects *Principle P5 – Autonomy with alignment*, as it allows each domain to maintain specific configurations while conforming to the shared eligibility rules of the data mesh.

Technically speaking, GoTriple is a multilayered web platform, composed of several interconnected parts, whose main components are:

- the SCRE processing pipeline, that parametrically harvests and processes content from multiple sources (around 1,400 at present) which expose their data through standard protocols (i.e., OAI-PMH, REST) or as data dumps in open formats (i.e., XML, JSON)
- the back-end of the web platform, which manages the business logic to implement the users' actions on the platform, e.g., search, registration, authentication, document claiming for authors
- the front-end of GoTriple.eu, which is the web interface through which users experience the application

GoTriple has been designed to deal with SSH content from the very beginning, but at the same time many of the existing components and services operate according to a parametric logic that allows for a domain-agnostic application of their features. For example, the SCRE pipeline works on content sources whose harvesting parameters are specified by the platform administrators via a web interface. Therefore it can operate on any kind of source, not only on those related to SSH.

On the other hand, other components are solely laid out for the SSH domain, which are enlisted below:

- SCRE component:
 - the CORDIS connector for projects looks only for projects classified with SSH related categories according to the European Science Vocabulary (EuroSciVoc)
 - the classifier service is based on a machine learning trained model which associates documents and projects to 27 disciplines from the TRIPLE Ontology³³ (which is based on categories previously defined in the MORESS research project³⁴)
 - the annotator service matches the content of document and project descriptions with the labels of the SSH SKOS based TRIPLE Vocabulary
- GoTriple website (back-end and front-end):
 - the disciplines section is based on the 27 SSH disciplines mentioned above
 - the user registration process has some attributes that mostly relate to an SSH-affiliated audience (e.g., "Type of user", "Your interests").

³³ <https://gotriple.eu/ontology/triple>

³⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/HPSE-CT-2002-60060/f r>

Generalizing most of these components will not be overly complicated. However, applying alternative strategies, for example including the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Large Language Models, to generalise the current classifier, will pose a greater challenge. Further, AI plays a fundamental role in LUMEN. During the course of the project an AI Chatbot will be developed and integrated, first on GoTriple.eu and then on the White-Label Platform, with the aim to provide an alternative and efficient paradigm for information retrieval in the discovery platforms, by enabling users to easily find answers to research questions while directly interacting with the platform's content collection.

By facilitating direct interactions and providing easy access to a wide range of academic materials, the AI Chatbot can be an effective paradigm for academic resource discovery. It not only makes research more efficient but also enhances the overall user experience by making academic materials more accessible and easier to discover.

The GoTriple Chatbot, a prototype implemented as a proof of concept to validate this new paradigm for accessing GoTriple's content, has already been put in practice. It currently features a limited number of documents (around 3,100) in five different languages, all concerning a common list of topics. This prototype has been used by a restricted audience of SSH researchers, which provided extremely positive feedback. Given this favorable response, in LUMEN we will develop a complete AI chatbot service named *AIDA (AI Driven Discovery Assistant)*, built on this initial experiment. It will provide access to the full range of content indexed by the various discovery platforms, along with additional user services, including the possibility to interact with a personalised collection of documents, in a fashion similar to what Google's NotebookLM offers. For this work, a dedicated task has been planned in LUMEN (T6.2), whose activities are going to start at month 7.

To improve the user experience on both GoTriple and the White-Label Discovery Platform, we are introducing a suite of advanced visualisation tools, which will provide dynamic and intuitive visual aids that make discovering and interacting with data easier and more effective.

GoTriple already implemented interactive tools, namely the Knowledge Map³⁵ and the Streamgraph³⁶, that produce visualisations based on the result of a user's search: the former puts together in different clusters documents that cover similar topics; the latter shows the evolution of the main topics of the search result over time. Despite being graphically appealing, these tools have significant drawbacks, such as very high response times and limited synchronisations with GoTriple indexes which cause different documents being visualised than returned by the search.

³⁵

https://gotriple.eu/knowledgeMap?q=digital%20education&from=1802-01-01&to=2023-04-26&lang_id=all-lang

³⁶ https://gotriple.eu/streamgraph?q=news&from=1748-01-01&to=2023-04-26&lang_id=all-lang

In LUMEN, completely new visualisation tools will be implemented, on the one hand to overcome the aforementioned limitations, and on the other hand to enhance user experience and facilitate the ways users interact with search results and understand complex information. These tools will be tested and validated through real-world LUMEN Use Cases, ensuring their relevance and usability across domains. Visualisations will provide new graphic interfaces and will be designed to create engaging and insightful interactions besides guaranteeing fast response times. Their development will follow the latest user experience principles and will be based on an extensive user analysis. Finally, all discovery platforms will include a set of APIs to facilitate the integration in the data mesh ecosystem. Platforms based on the White-Label technology will thus be able to expose and exchange data in a federated manner, in alignment with *Principle P3 – Contractual interoperability*, which ensures that all interfaces conform to the structured conditions and expectations defined in the corresponding data contracts.

3.2.2 The LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (LUMIS)

The LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (LUMIS) aims to fill a gap for knowledge experts, ontologists, taxonomists by integrating usual open source tools together into a coherent workflow enabling the creation and management of FAIR-by-design semantic artefacts (i.e. formal ontologies, thesauri, controlled vocabularies,...). This platform should support the creation, the testing and the publication of semantic artefacts as well as the maintenance and governance of these artefacts. It also includes the possibility to FAIRifying and/or reuse existing semantic artefacts, to align them together and to use them to enrich the metadata with domain specific semantic artefacts. For this purpose, the platform will provide standardised API to enable the connection of existing tools for the enrichment and harmonisation of the metadata such as annotators, metadata/data converters,...

The semantic artefacts created, imported, transformed, FAIRified by the platform should be an integral part of the data mesh and considered as a data product. These Semantic Artefacts are major assets within the data mesh architecture by being both data products and by enabling the alignment of the various data products provided by the communities.

LUMIS will rely on existing open source tools that are often disconnected from each other but part of the semantic artefact development and quality checking process. Furthermore, the platform should align on a specific methodology such as the LOT methodology (Poveda-Villalón et al., 2022)^{37,38} which has been updated to support FAIR-by-design semantic artefact development in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT³⁹ project (Poveda-Villalón et al., 2023)⁴⁰.

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755>.

³⁸ <https://lot.linkeddata.es/>

³⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10551054>

LUMIS will play a major role in the LUMEN ecosystem by providing to the communities a platform for accessing FAIR-by-design semantic artefact for annotating and enriching their knowledge graph with domain specific semantic artefacts. It directly supports the LUMEN data mesh principle *P6 - Semantic decoupling with alignment*. Semantic artefacts developed or FAIRified in the platform will be published into existing thematic semantic artefacts catalogues such as EarthPortal⁴¹, BioPortal⁴², LOV⁴³, etc. These platforms provide access to the Semantic Artefact and its content through APIs which will be used to create a federation of semantic artefact repositories relying on the OntoPortal Federation, the implementation of the FAIR Semantic Artefact API developed in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT project (Wilson et al., 2024)⁴⁴. To support the extension of these federating capabilities, we will leverage the FAIRCat service (Le Franc et al., 2022)⁴⁵, developed in FAIRsFAIR project⁴⁶, to collect concepts and properties from various other semantic artefact repositories to create a unique index of concepts and properties which can be used for auto-completion function during the creation of semantic artefacts, the AI annotation workflow and many other functionalities.

Although LUMIS operates as a standalone service within the LUMEN federation, it plays a crucial role in enhancing the discovery experience offered by White-Label Platforms. The semantic artefacts curated and published via LUMIS can be directly consumed by other components, including the search interface or ingestion pipelines to enable domain-specific filtering, metadata enrichment, and intelligent retrieval. This integration reinforces the interoperability and semantic alignment of discovery platforms across the mesh, in line with *Principle P6* and the modular structure of the Common Discovery Infrastructure.

3.2.3 The Meta-Search Engine

In a federated ecosystem like LUMEN, where each community retains ownership of its platforms and data, discoverability across domains becomes a cornerstone for enabling interdisciplinary research and maximizing reuse. To address this, LUMEN introduces a dedicated Meta-Search Service, designed to operate at the intersection of community platforms, shared metadata, and AI-enhanced exploration features.

The Meta-Search engine serves as a cross-platform discovery component, capable of aggregating, linking, and querying data from multiple federated discovery platforms – regardless of their underlying technology or scientific domain (*P2 – Federated discovery*). It builds upon the metadata exposed through standardised interfaces as defined in the data contracts associated with each community's data products (*P3 – Contractual interoperability*).

Key features include:

⁴¹ <https://earthportal.eu/>

⁴² <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>

⁴³ <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12579779>

⁴⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675295>

⁴⁶ <http://fairsfair.eu/>

- Multilingual search, supporting content and metadata in multiple languages, with translation and enrichment pipelines ensuring accessibility across linguistic boundaries (P4 – *FAIR-by-design*).
- Semantic filtering and faceting, enabling users to refine results based on domain-specific ontologies and classifications exposed through LUMIS (P6 – *Semantic decoupling with alignment*).
- Contextual recommendation mechanisms, leveraging usage data, metadata similarity, and AI-driven heuristics to suggest related resources across communities.

The Meta-Search is part of the LUMEN Common Discovery Infrastructure and plays a central role in the delivery of LUMEN's interdisciplinary discovery experiences. It not only allows users to access resources (publications, dataset, software, etc.) across domains, but also acts as a backbone for more advanced applications such as the LUMEN Chatbot or metrics visualisation services.

Designed as a reusable, composable, and evolutive service (P7 – *Evolutive integration*), the Meta-Search supports integration both at the UI level (white label discovery platforms) and programmatically (API access), enabling community-specific interfaces to benefit from cross-domain capabilities without abandoning their local autonomy.

Ultimately, the Meta-Search service is a key enabler of LUMEN's vision: connecting communities through interoperable metadata and fostering serendipitous discovery across scientific silos.

3.2.4 Other LUMEN common components

Beyond the core pillars of the discovery infrastructure – the White-Label Discovery Platform, the LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (LUMIS), and the Meta-Search Engine, LUMEN includes a broader set of **shared technical components** that support the discoverability, usability, and interoperability of data products across the federation.

These components respond to recurring needs identified by the communities during the early phases of the project: simplifying user interaction, enabling guided exploration, monitoring impact, and ensuring the visibility and traceability of scientific resources. They are not limited to a specific scientific domain or platform. Instead, they are designed to be modular, reusable, and interoperable, and are integrated into the mesh according to two main patterns:

- Some components are **embedded** directly within the White-Label Discovery Platform. These services are instantiated for each community and tailored to local needs, while benefiting from a common technical base.
- Others are developed as **shared services**, hosted independently and accessed through standardised APIs. These components operate across communities

and discovery platforms, contributing to the federation as transversal building blocks.

Two additional components are particularly relevant in this context:

Metrics Services

Understanding how data products are accessed, reused, and cited is essential for communities to measure their scientific and societal impact. To support this, LUMEN will provide a **modular metrics service** that calculates usage statistics (views, downloads), as well as citation and interlinking indicators (e.g. via OpenCitations or internal graphs).

Unlike visualisations or the chatbot, this service will be developed as a standalone component, accessible via API. It will feed metrics dashboards embedded in discovery platforms, but will also be available for external reuse, for instance in evaluation workflows or in EOSC-related observatories.

Automatically Built Software Catalogue

Software is a first-class scientific object, yet it is often poorly indexed and disconnected from the rest of the research ecosystem. LUMEN addresses this by developing a software catalogue service, which aggregates and enriches metadata about open-source research software from multiple sources (e.g. HAL, Zenodo, Software Heritage). Operating as an independent system, the catalogue will be connected to discovery platforms through APIs and data contracts, and will contribute to the broader LUMEN knowledge graph. The service will support the structured exposure of software records, including descriptive metadata, versioning, and licensing. In the future, these records may also reference related publications, datasets, or projects, provided that such associations are made available by communities or data providers.

Taken together, these components reflect the architectural flexibility of the LUMEN federation. By distinguishing between components that are locally instantiated (within discovery platforms) and those that are shared across communities, LUMEN balances the principles of autonomy (P5) and alignment (P3, P7). This layered strategy ensures that new features can be developed once and reused widely, while preserving the ability of each community to adapt the discovery experience to its own needs.

3.3 Federated Data Sharing Governance

The Federated Data Sharing Governance in LUMEN defines the shared framework through which autonomous scientific communities coordinate the exposure, validation, and integration of their data products. It enables collaboration without

centralisation, by aligning independently operated platforms, components, and services through a common set of rules, data contracts, and validation processes.

3.3.1 *The governance model*

At this early stage of the project, this governance model is being progressively structured. A detailed and operational implementation will be developed under Task 7.4, which is responsible for formalising the rules, roles, and cycles that will support the Federated Shared Data Governance layer of the LUMEN architecture.

The governance model in LUMEN is conceived as a distributed layer, enabling communities to progressively align their contributions while retaining local autonomy. Rather than introducing a formal governance entity from the outset, the project emphasises a pragmatic and evolutionary approach. Governance roles will emerge organically through collaborative practices such as data contract validation, interoperability checks, and the implementation of shared quality and compliance policies – particularly those related to EOSC integration.

As part of this federated model, LUMEN introduces the concept of a community guild, a coordinated structure composed of designated community representatives (e.g., data providers, researchers, developer), technical stakeholders and community liaisons. The liaison is a formally identified contact person who ensures communication and alignment between their community and the broader federation. The guild's role is not to act as a rigid committee, but to serve as a lightweight coordination space where participants can jointly review data contracts, interpret federation eligibility criteria, and share responsibility for aligning with cross-domain interoperability standards.

At this stage, this governance layer remains conceptual and non-binding, allowing flexibility and progressive engagement. The actual structure, responsibilities, and decision-making processes of the governance model will be defined and formalised during Task 7.4, once sufficient practices and needs have emerged across the federation.

During the initial phase of the project, the LUMEN technical team is defining and validating a core set of specifications, including data product identification rules, initial data source connectivity, standardised data contract templates, supported metadata formats, and exposure protocols (such as REST, OAI-PMH, or CSW). This work is conducted in close coordination with domain stakeholders already engaged in the federation, ensuring that early technical choices reflect real-world needs and practices. These foundational elements will serve as the starting point for broader, community-driven governance cycles, progressively shaping shared validation procedures and alignment rules.

This federated governance structure directly supports Principle P8 – Distributed governance, by ensuring that decisions are taken collectively by communities through the guild, and Principle P3 – Contractual interoperability, by enforcing shared validation of data contracts. It also supports Principle P7 – Evolutive integration,

allowing communities with different levels of maturity to progressively join the federation while aligning with shared discovery and governance rules.

3.3.2 Structure and functions of the governance layer

Building on the foundational principles presented above, the Federated Shared Data Governance layer of LUMEN will provide a lightweight but structured coordination framework. This layer will not impose central authority, but instead promote distributed governance, rooted in shared responsibilities, domain autonomy, and alignment with common interoperability rules.

Its primary objective is to ensure that data products exposed by diverse communities are validated, governed, and integrated in a coherent, reusable, and trusted manner across the federation. This will be achieved by enabling a coordinated governance process involving community representatives, technical coordinators, and the LUMEN technical team.

Core Responsibilities

At this stage, the following governance functions are foreseen:

- **Define and maintain federation-wide policies**, including validation rules, interoperability requirements, and metadata quality thresholds.
- **Review and validate data contracts**, to ensure consistency with FAIR principles and LUMEN eligibility criteria.
- **Promote the reuse of existing protocols and formats**, such as REST APIs, OAI-PMH, CSW, OGC API, and MOD-API, in order to minimise integration costs and maximise interoperability.
- **Oversee the progressive onboarding of legacy systems**, supporting gradual transitions to machine-actionable and contract-governed exposure models.
- **Coordinate alignment with EOSC interoperability frameworks**, including AAI, PID services, and semantic standards.
- **Ensure alignment of exposed metadata with the LUMEN Data Model**, by validating semantic mappings, promoting convergence on common vocabularies, and overseeing their consistent application across federated data sources.
- **Validate and accept community contributions** to common services (e.g., Meta-Search, LUMIS, White-Label Platforms), ensuring consistency and quality.

These responsibilities will be **refined and operationalised during Task 7.4**, which is charged with the formal development of the governance processes, roles, and validation procedures.

Cycles of Review and Adaptation

To maintain semantic consistency and data quality over time, the governance layer will implement **periodic review cycles**. These cycles will allow communities to collectively:

- Adapt data contracts to evolving needs or standards;
- Review compliance with Data Quality Policies;
- Address emerging interoperability issues;
- Improve metadata practices (e.g. multilingual support, schema alignment, use of controlled vocabularies).

These shared cycles will support the long-term cohesion and evolutive nature of the federation, while offering flexibility to adjust based on experience.

Progressive Onboarding and Eligibility

Recognising the heterogeneous maturity levels of participating communities, the LUMEN governance model adopts a progressive onboarding strategy. Communities may start by exposing a limited number of well-described data products, without immediately conforming to all federation requirements. Over time, they can expand their contributions, formalise contracts, and integrate additional services.

Eligibility rules for onboarding data products and data sources will be gradually refined based on experience and domain-specific constraints. These rules will define what qualifies a data source as connectable, what metadata quality is expected, and what contract roles (producer, enhancer, aggregator, reference) are applicable.

Towards Sustainability and Scalability

A long-term ambition of the LUMEN governance model is to support a sustainable and extensible federation, capable of evolving beyond the project's timeline. To this end:

- The framework is domain-agnostic by design, supporting interdisciplinary use cases;
- It promotes alignment with European standards and EOSC governance principles;
- It supports the development of reusable tools (e.g., semantic artefacts, visualisation components) that enable communities to operate independently, while remaining interoperable.

By encouraging shared validation procedures, gradual adoption pathways, and cross-community alignment, the LUMEN governance layer embodies:

- *Principle P8 – Distributed governance*, through the coordination role of the community guild;
- *Principle P3 – Contractual interoperability*, via data contract validation and enforcement;
- *Principle P7 – Evolutive integration*, by supporting incremental onboarding and flexible technical integration.

3.3.3 Operational link between governance and implementation

To ensure that governance decisions are grounded in real implementation practices, the governance layer is not limited to abstract validation. It is directly connected to the lifecycle of data products, data sources, and the data contracts that bind them.

In LUMEN, each data product is exposed through one or more data sources, and each exposure is governed by a dedicated data contract. While the governance body does not intervene in the internal management of data products or the technical configuration of data sources, it validates the conditions under which a product is federated, through the review of its associated contract.

This process combines technical validation, e.g. schema conformance, machine-actionability, semantic alignment, with governance review, which examines whether the contract complies with federation-wide expectations (e.g. licensing, access policies, metadata standards, update guarantees).

Technically, contracts are authored and versioned in YAML using the ODCS model. Validation workflows combine automated checks (e.g. syntax, completeness) and human oversight performed by community liaisons and federation coordinators.

By embedding these checks in the governance cycle, LUMEN ensures that federated exposure is not only technically compliant but also socially endorsed by the involved communities. This alignment between contract implementation and governance guarantees transparency, accountability, and trust across the federation.

3.4 Infrastructure & Scalability considerations

The LUMEN federation relies on a distributed, evolutive infrastructure that supports the progressive deployment, integration, and scaling of discovery services across heterogeneous community environments. While each component of the architecture must accommodate the specific needs and constraints of individual scientific domains, the overall system is designed to ensure interoperability, modularity, and long-term sustainability.

This section outlines the architectural principles, deployment strategies, and interoperability mechanisms that guide the implementation of the LUMEN infrastructure, from local community deployments to integration with EOSC and cloud-native scalability practices. These considerations reflect and operationalise several key LUMEN principles, including *P1 – Domain ownership*, *P5 – Autonomy with alignment*, and *P7 – Evolutive integration*.

3.4.1 Distributed Infrastructure Principles

The LUMEN data mesh is designed as a federated and evolutive ecosystem, where each community retains control over its own infrastructure, while contributing to a coherent shared architecture. This section outlines the core infrastructure principles that support this model, enabling interoperability without enforcing uniformity.

Community-based deployment and decentralisation

Each community in LUMEN is encouraged to deploy and operate its own local stack, including metadata services, discovery interfaces, or knowledge graph components – aligned with *Principle P1 – Domain ownership*. These services are tailored to local needs and may evolve independently, as long as they expose metadata and data products via interoperable interfaces.

However, not all components can or should be redeployed in every context. Some key services, such as the Meta-Search Engine, LUMIS, and the Metrics Services are implemented as common components, designed for shared use across the federation. These services may be hosted centrally during the initial phase of the project, but the architecture supports their progressive redeployment within community infrastructures when local capacity or strategic alignment allows it.

This hybrid model reflects a pragmatic interpretation of *Principle P5 – Autonomy with alignment*: communities retain sovereignty over their core data services, while relying on a set of modular, reusable, and transparent shared services to support federation-wide discovery and enrichment workflows.

These questions of long-term hosting, operational responsibility, and service redeployment will be addressed throughout the project *within the scope of WP5 Interoperability and EOSC integration*.

Resilience and autonomy by design

While decentralised deployments promote fault isolation at the local level, the availability of shared services based on the LUMEN common components becomes a key point of attention. A failure in a central component, such as the Meta-Search, could temporarily impact all users. This is why LUMEN adopts a cloud-native, containerised deployment strategy, with monitoring, redundancy, and scalability features integrated from the outset.

Common components are initially hosted within the Common Discovery Infrastructure layer operated by LUMEN technical partners. This environment ensures performance, security, and maintenance across the project duration. In parallel, the architecture explicitly anticipates future multi-node hosting scenarios, where communities or service providers can rehost components like the chatbot or LUMIS independently, thereby distributing operational responsibility and reducing central dependencies over time.

This strategy aligns with Principle P7 – Evolutive integration, by enabling each community to gradually take control of parts of the shared infrastructure – not as a prerequisite, but as an optional, strategic step toward long-term sustainability and autonomy.

These aspects of infrastructure planning and sustainability will be further developed and coordinated within WP5, as part of LUMEN’s long-term operational roadmap.

Interoperability through interfaces and metadata

In a federated architecture such as LUMEN’s, interoperability is the key enabler that allows distributed systems to function as a coherent ecosystem. Rather than requiring technological uniformity, LUMEN ensures integration through the exposure of data products and services via standardised APIs and metadata schemas.

Each community is expected to make its resources discoverable through well-defined, machine-actionable interfaces and to expose their metadata using community-specific schemas and formats, according to disciplinary conventions and existing platforms.

At the federation level, data product metadata is structured using a shared profile based on DCAT, enriched with LUMEN-specific extensions. This ensures alignment and interoperability across the mesh, while preserving flexibility and autonomy at the local level.

This interface-driven approach provides the semantic and technical glue that connects heterogeneous platforms and components across the federation. It enables scalable and evolutive integration patterns, aligned with *Principle P7 – Evolutive integration*, and supports metadata harvesting, cross-platform discovery, and enrichment workflows, without imposing centralised infrastructure decisions.

This model is what makes the distributed infrastructure of LUMEN operable as a federation, allowing each community to participate with its own stack while remaining aligned through shared interoperability standards.

3.4.2 EOSC Integration

LUMEN is committed to progressively aligning its components with the emerging EOSC Federation architecture. Rather than integrating into the deprecated EOSC Exchange, LUMEN’s integration strategy focuses on contributing to and interoperating with the EOSC Federation through recognised EOSC Nodes, in compliance with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC IF)[18] and the federating capabilities defined in the EOSC Federation Handbook[19].

Integration with EOSC Node Core Capabilities

Several LUMEN components, such as the White-Label Discovery Platform, LUMIS, and the Meta-Search Engine are designed to be exposed as EOSC services through

one or more EOSC Nodes. To ensure seamless integration, LUMEN will align with the following Node Core Capabilities, as outlined in the EOSC architecture:

- Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI): Integration with EOSC AAI (AARC Blueprint-compliant) will enable federated access and identity federation for users of LUMEN services.
- Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): All data products exposed via LUMEN will comply with EOSC PID policies to ensure traceability, citability, and uniqueness.
- Service Monitoring, Accounting, and Helpdesk: LUMEN will explore compatibility with the EOSC Federation's monitoring and support services, with operational alignment handled progressively.

These integration efforts reflect *Principle P7 – Evolutive Integration* and will be coordinated through WP5, which brings strong expertise in EOSC technical alignment.

Contribution to the EOSC Federation

LUMEN also contributes to provide reusable, domain-agnostic services that are eligible for onboarding into EOSC Nodes and exposure as EOSC Federated Capabilities. These include:

- The White-Label Discovery Platform, deployable across disciplines as a configurable EOSC-aligned discovery interface. This platform could be onboarded as a tool in the EOSC EU Node and referenced in the EOSC EU Node Tool Hub⁴⁷, supporting discoverability through standardised service catalogues.
- LUMIS, enabling FAIR-by-design creation and curation of semantic artefacts, with publication to federated catalogues.
- The LUMEN Meta-Search Engine, supporting cross-domain discovery and interoperability via EOSC-aligned APIs.
- Advanced components such as the AI-powered Chatbot, metrics dashboards, and visualisation modules.

Together, these services embody the spirit of the EOSC Federation as a “system of systems”. They are designed to be modular, composable, and standards-based, supporting both onboarding into EOSC Nodes and contribution to the broader European Open Science ecosystem.

Strategic Alignment

By participating in the EOSC Federation, LUMEN contributes to:

- Building the Common European Data Space for R&I;
- Aligning community-specific services with European interoperability and governance frameworks;

⁴⁷

https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2025-05/EOSC%20EU%20Node%20-%20Tools%20Hub%20Guide%20v1.4_0.pdf

- Expanding the FAIR research service portfolio available to researchers and infrastructures across Europe.

This strategy reflects LUMEN's dual ambition: ensuring short-term operational value for its communities while positioning its assets for long-term integration and sustainability within the EOSC landscape.

3.4.3 Cloud deployment for LUMEN components

The technical infrastructure used to host LUMEN components will be designed as a scalable, resilient, and evolutive cloud environment. Developed and operated within the scope of WP5, coordinated by the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center[20] (PSNC), this infrastructure will provide the foundation for both shared and community-specific services. It will ensure that these services can operate efficiently, scale according to demand, and support progressive re-deployment within individual community environments as needed.

Scalable and containerised by design

All LUMEN components and services, including discovery platforms, enrichment pipelines, and common components such as the Meta-Search Engine or Chatbot , will be deployed using containerisation and orchestration technologies, notably Docker and Kubernetes (or compatible distributions such as OKD). This approach will ensure modularity, portability, and rapid deployment across different environments.

The infrastructure, operated by PSNC, will support dynamic allocation of computing resources (CPU, memory, storage, network), enabling services to automatically scale up or down based on usage.

Deployments will adopt cloud-native patterns such as blue-green deployments, ensuring uninterrupted service availability during upgrades. Service images will be managed through container registries, allowing version control and continuous delivery practices.

Horizontal scalability and fault tolerance

LUMEN's architecture will adopt a horizontally scalable model, where services can handle increased demand by spawning additional, independent instances. These instances will be stateless, simplifying load balancing and reducing infrastructure complexity. Statelessness also eliminates single points of failure: in case of error, traffic can be rerouted without compromising availability, assuming adequate replication is in place.

This design supports both high availability and resilience across the federation, even in the presence of localised failures or community-specific outages.

Progressive re-deployment and sustainability

While core services will initially be hosted centrally by PSNC, the infrastructure will allow communities to rehost selected components within their own environments as technical capacity and strategic priorities evolve. This includes services like the Chatbot, FSAMS, or metrics dashboards.

Each component will be packaged as a portable container, ensuring that communities can operate them independently if needed – while remaining compatible with federation-wide protocols and governance.

This deployment strategy aligns with:

- *Principle P5 – Autonomy with alignment*, by enabling local control without compromising systemic cohesion;
- *Principle P7 – Evolutive integration*, by allowing incremental adoption of cloud-native practices and supporting long-term sustainability.

4. Conclusion & next steps

4.1 Key takeaways

The LUMEN Data Mesh does more than define an architecture – it offers a reframing of how scientific infrastructures can evolve in a fragmented, multilingual, and multi-disciplinary research landscape. Rather than striving for integration through centralisation or uniformity, LUMEN proposes a model where coordination emerges from structured autonomy, negotiated interoperability, and shared governance principles. This model embraces diversity not as a problem to be solved, but as the necessary condition for a federation that reflects the reality of scientific ecosystems: heterogeneous, distributed, and historically situated.

What emerges from this architecture is not a fixed system, but a dynamic framework capable of evolving alongside its communities. The combined use of semantically qualified data products and verifiable data contracts introduces a vocabulary of alignment that does not constrain innovation. On the contrary, it enables trust to circulate between actors without enforcing rigid harmonisation. It becomes possible to expose, link, and govern resources across domains without erasing their contextual richness – a balance that has long remained elusive in data infrastructures.

Crucially, LUMEN reframes governance itself: not as a top-down mechanism for control, but as a distributed trust infrastructure. The federation is not built from a central authority but from the capacity of its members to negotiate responsibilities, validate shared conditions, and progressively converge through dialogue and semantic alignment. This approach turns governance into a productive, community-led process – one that can adapt over time to new disciplines, new workflows, and emerging technical possibilities.

Seen from this angle, the LUMEN architecture is less a solution than a commitment: a commitment to openness without fragmentation, interoperability without erasure, and automation without opacity. It provides a scaffold for federated science that remains compatible with European policy goals (EOSC, FAIR), but does so in a way that respects the complexity of research cultures and infrastructures. In this sense, LUMEN does not simply federate services – it federates capacities, intentions, and futures.

4.2 Next steps

The architecture outlined in this deliverable provides the conceptual backbone for the LUMEN federation. The next steps will activate each layer of this architecture through coordinated developments across the project's technical Work Packages, consolidating the LUMEN data mesh as a coherent and scalable infrastructure for scientific knowledge discovery and interoperability.

At the semantic layer, Deliverable D4.2 will formalise the LUMEN Data Model, defining the structure and validation rules of semantically enriched data products and data contracts. This effort, led by T4.1 in collaboration with WP2, will provide the foundations for the deployment of LUMIS (T2.1).

At the infrastructure layer, the federation will operationalise its shared services through WP5, with Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 ensuring containerisation, orchestration, and integration with EOSC Core services such as AAI and PID systems. The deployment of the White-Label Discovery Platform (T4.2) will serve as the main entry point for community-specific portals, while the Meta-Search Engine (T6.1) will build on these platforms to offer interdisciplinary discovery services. This meta-search tool, led by Foxcub, will integrate multilingual search and will rely on the metadata exposure mechanisms and data contract interfaces specified in the Data Model.

Alongside the deployment of the interdisciplinary meta-search service (T6.1), which will enable multilingual and cross-platform discovery based on the metadata and contracts defined in WP4 and validated through T7.4, several complementary services are planned to enhance researchers' access to and interaction with scientific resources across the federation. The LUMEN chatbot (T6.2) will introduce new conversational discovery experiences, relying on open-source large language models fine-tuned for domain-specific knowledge and interfaced with the federated discovery platforms. This shift from query-based access to guided dialogue will open inclusive and intuitive pathways for research exploration. Meanwhile, metrics services (T6.3) will provide visibility into the usage, visibility, and open-access status of publications and data products exposed through LUMEN. Finally, interactive visualisation tools (T6.4) will be integrated into all discovery platforms to facilitate intuitive, pattern-driven exploration of results, reinforcing the usability and engagement of the LUMEN infrastructure.

At the governance and federation layer, Task 7.4 will be instrumental in consolidating the LUMEN governance model. This includes formalising procedures for onboarding, compliance, and contract validation, and ensuring coherence across all layers of the federation.

Finally, the implementation will be driven by community engagement through WP3, which will coordinate pilot activities across diverse scientific domains. These pilots will play a dual role: validating technical components under real conditions, and informing governance and modelling decisions through continuous feedback loops.

Together, these steps will transition the LUMEN architecture from a conceptual framework to a distributed, FAIR-aligned, and community-anchored infrastructure, bridging disciplinary boundaries while respecting autonomy, and building a shared space for discovery, negotiation, and long-term stewardship of research outputs.

References

1. Goedegebuure, A., Kumara, I., Driessen, S., Van Den Heuvel, W.-J., Monsieur, G., Tamburri, D. A., & Di Nucci, D. (2024). *Data mesh: A Systematic Gray Literature Review*. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 57(1), Article 11. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3687301>
2. Dehghani, Z. (2019). *How to Move Beyond a Monolithic Data Lake to a Distributed data mesh*. *martinfowler.com*. <https://martinfowler.com/articles/data-monolith-to-mesh.html>
3. Wilkinson, M. D., et al. (2016). *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
4. Machado, I. A., Costa, C., & Santos, M. Y. (2022). *Data mesh: Concepts and Principles of a Paradigm Shift in Data Architectures*. *Procedia Computer Science*, 196, 263–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.12.013>
5. Google Cloud. (2022, March 16). *How eDreams ODIGEO improved data trust and agility using Data Mesh on Google Cloud*. *Google Cloud Blog*. <https://cloud.google.com/blog/products/data-analytics/how-edreams-odigeo-implemented-data-mesh-on-google-cloud>
6. Jacobsen, A., de Miranda Azevedo, R., Juty, N., et al. (2020). *FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations*. *Data Intelligence*, 2(1–2), 10–29. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_r_00024
7. Schultes, E., Wittenburg, P., & Bonino da Silva Santos, L. O. (2020). *FAIR Data Point: A pragmatic approach to FAIR implementation*. *Data Intelligence*, 2(1–2), 291–297. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_0004
8. Dehghani, Z. (2022). *Data mesh: Delivering data-driven value at scale*. O'Reilly Media.
9. Gregory, A., Bell, D., Brickley, D., Buttigieg, P. L., Cox, S., Edwards, M., Doug, F., Gonzalez Morales, L. G., Heus, P., Hodson, S., Kanjala, C., Le Franc, Y., Maxwell, L., Molloy, L., Richard, S., Rizzolo, F., Winstanley, P., Wyborn, L., & Burton, A. (2024). *WorldFAIR (D2.3) Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) (Version 1)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236871>
10. DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). *DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data v4.4*. <https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69>

11. Software Heritage & CodeMeta Project. (2021). *CodeMeta: An exchange schema for software metadata*. <https://codemeta.github.io/>
12. DPDS. (2023). *Data Product Descriptor Specification*. Open Data Mesh. <https://dpds.opendatamesh.org>
13. Dehghani, Z. (2022). *Data Product Canvas*. Data Mesh Architecture. <https://www.datamesh-architecture.com/data-product-canvas>
14. Kekäläinen, P. (2023). *Standardized data product metadata – examples based on real-world published data products*. Medium. <https://medium.com/@kyyberi>
15. W3C. (2020). *Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) – Version 3*. W3C Recommendation. <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/> dd
16. Guha, R. V., Brickley, D., & MacBeth, S. (2016). *Schema.org: Evolution of Structured Data on the Web*. *Communications of the ACM*, 59(2), 44–51. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2844544>
17. Landel, S., Kraaikamp, E., Thorpe, D. E., Ashley, K., Davidson, J., Jasinska, A., Boerman, S., Caminha Juaçaba Neto, R., & Gonzalez, E. (2025). *D6.3 - MoU and SLA templates for data interoperability (V1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770711>
18. Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K., Ojsteršek, M., Choirat, C., van de Sanden, M., & Coppens, F. (2021). *EOSC Interoperability Framework (v1.0)*. Publications Office of the European Union.
19. EOSC Association. (2025). *EOSC Federation Handbook (Version 1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>
20. Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center. (2024). *LUMEN – Operating Freely Across a Variety of Scientific Fields*. <https://www.psnk.pl/lumen-operating-freely-across-a-variety-of-scientific-fields/>
21. Parra, C., Baez, M., Daniel, F., Casati, F., Marchese, M., & Cernuzzi, L. (2010). *A Scientific Resource Space Management System* (Technical Report DISI-10-013). University of Trento. <http://eprints.biblio.unitn.it/archive/00001812/>
22. EOSC Task Force on Software and Services. (2023). *SIRS Gap Analysis Report [Deliverable]*. EOSC Association. <https://eosc.eu/task-force-deliverab/sirs-gap-analysis-report/>
23. Wilkinson, M. D., et al. (2016). *The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

24. European Commission. (2018). *Turning FAIR into reality: Final report and action plan from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR data*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524>
25. Lamprecht, A.-L., Garcia, L., Kuzak, M., et al. (2019). *Towards FAIR principles for research software*. *Data Science*, 3(1), 37–59. <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026>
26. EOSC Association. (2023). *EOSC Federation Handbook*. <https://zenodo.org/record/14999577>
27. Corcho, O., Ekaputra, F. J., Heibi, I., et al. (2024). A maturity model for catalogues of semantic artefacts. *Scientific Data*, 11, 479. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03185-4>
28. Poveda-Villalón, M., Fernández-Izquierdo, A., Fernández-López, M., & García-Castro, R. (2022). LOT: An industrial oriented ontology engineering framework. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 111, 104755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755>
29. Poveda-Villalón, M., Garijo, D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Le Franc, Y., Jonquet, C., Aubin, S., Soiland-Reyes, S., Goble, C., & Kechagioglou, X. (2023). *M4.2 - Processes & tools to engineer FAIR semantic artefacts*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10551054>
30. Wilson, A., & Jonquet, C. (2024). *D4.3 - Specification of shared metadata description of semantic artefacts and their catalogues including common reference API (V1.0 - Draft not yet approved by the European Commission)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12579779>
31. Le Franc, Y., Bonino, L., Koivula, H., Parland-von Essen, J., & Pergl, R. (2022). *D2.8 FAIR Semantics Recommendations Third Iteration (V1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675295>
32. Perrin, J.-G. (2022, August 3). The next generation of Data Platforms is the Data Mesh. The PayPal Technology Blog. <https://medium.com/paypal-tech/the-next-generation-of-data-platforms-is-the-data-mesh-6158f0455c6c>
33. Debruyne, C., Wimalaratne, S. M., Fathy, Y., & Loutas, N. (2023). *The Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275721>
34. Soiland-Reyes, S., Sefton, P., Crosas, M., Castro, L. J., Miksa, T., Katz, D. S., ... Goble, C. (2022). Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate. *Data Science*, 5(1), 97–138. <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210053>

35. Dumontier, M., Baker, C. J. O., Baran, J., Callahan, A., Chepelev, L., Cruz-Toledo, J., ... Hoehndorf, R. (2014). The SemanticScience Integrated Ontology (SIO) for biomedical research and knowledge discovery. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 5(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2041-1480-5-14>

Annex 1. Extended Glossary and Conceptual Notes

This section contains the complete set of definitions used throughout the LUMEN Data Mesh Architecture Framework, following the conventions outlined in ISO 704:2022⁴⁸. Each term is provided with extended explanations, context-specific notes, and, where relevant, conceptual diagrams to support in-depth understanding and semantic precision. This annex serves as a comprehensive reference for contributors and reviewers who wish to examine the full conceptual, technical, and organisational scope underpinning the document.

Index

Mesh (or Data Mesh).....	9
Data Mesh Architecture Framework.....	9
Resource (or Scientific Resource).....	9
Data Product.....	9
Data Source.....	9
Data Contract.....	9
Metadata.....	10
Hosting.....	10
Exposing.....	10
Common Data Model (or LUMEN Data Model).....	10
FAIR Principles.....	10
Domain Ownership.....	10
Decentralisation.....	10
Federation (or LUMEN Federation).....	10
Community (or Scientific Community).....	10
Connected Communities.....	10
Community Liaison.....	11
Technical Coordinator.....	11
Guild (or Community Guild).....	11
Individual.....	11
Organisation.....	11
Agent.....	11
Agent profile.....	11
Research Literature.....	11
Dataset.....	11
Software.....	12
Semantic Artefact.....	12
Multimedia asset.....	12
Project.....	12

⁴⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79077.html>

Layer.....	12
Connected Communities Ecosystem.....	12
Common Discovery Infrastructure.....	12
Federated Shared Data Governance.....	12
Component.....	13
Service.....	13
Interface.....	13
Protocol.....	13
Platform (or Portal).....	13
Catalogue.....	13
Core Discovery Asset.....	13
White-Label Discovery Platform.....	13
LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (or LUMIS).....	13
Meta-Search (or Meta-Search Engine).....	13
A. Main Data Mesh Concepts.....	76
Mesh (or Data Mesh).....	76
Data Mesh Architecture Framework.....	77
Resource (or Scientific Resource).....	77
Data Product.....	78
Data Source.....	78
Data Contract.....	78
Metadata (or Data Product Metadata).....	79
Hosting.....	79
Exposing.....	79
Common Data Model (or LUMEN Data Model).....	79
B. Principles.....	80
FAIR Principles.....	80
Domain Ownership.....	81
Decentralisation.....	81
Federation (or LUMEN Federation).....	81
C. Communities & Actors.....	82
Community (or Scientific Community).....	82
Connected Communities.....	82
Community Liaison.....	83
Technical Coordinator.....	83
Guild (or Community Guild).....	83
D. Scientific Resources.....	84
Individual.....	84
Organisation.....	84

Agent.....	84
Agent profile.....	85
Research Literature.....	85
Dataset.....	85
Software.....	86
Semantic Artefact.....	86
Multimedia asset.....	86
Project.....	86
E. Conceptual Architecture.....	87
Layer.....	87
Connected Communities Ecosystem.....	88
Common Discovery Infrastructure.....	88
Federated Shared Data Governance.....	88
Component.....	89
Service.....	89
Interface.....	89
Protocol.....	89
Platform (or Portal).....	90
Catalogue.....	90
F. Core Discovery Assets.....	91
Core Discovery Asset.....	91
White-Label Discovery Platform.....	92
LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (or LUMIS).....	92
Meta-Search (or Meta-Search Engine).....	92

A. Main Data Mesh Concepts

Mesh (or Data Mesh)

Decentralised data architecture paradigm in which *data* is treated as a product, owned and governed by domain teams, integrated through a federated infrastructure and based on four foundational principles[8]:

- Domain-oriented data ownership and architecture, covering both the structuring of data and the design of services and components enabling their exposure, governance, and interoperability
- Data as a product
- Self-serve data infrastructure as a platform
- Federated governance

Note 1: In LUMEN, *data* is considered one type of scientific resource.

Note 2: In LUMEN, the data mesh is adapted to scientific contexts: communities retain autonomy over their data and platforms, while exposing well-defined data products governed by data contracts.

Note 3: The LUMEN implementation of the data mesh supports FAIR principles, accommodates domain-specific diversity and ensures progressive and scalable integration with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Note 4: This model enables interoperability, discoverability, and reuse of data products across an evolving federation of connected communities.

Data Mesh Architecture Framework

Structured architectural model that formalises the LUMEN vision of the data mesh, by describing the conceptual layers, technical components, and federation mechanisms that enable communities to expose, discover, and govern their data products collaboratively.

Note 1: It operationalises the principles of domain ownership, interoperability, and decentralisation by aligning community-driven practices with shared discovery services and governance rules.

Note 2: It provides a reference model for integrating diverse platforms through standardised protocols, metadata exposure, and lightweight governance, supporting gradual alignment across communities.

Note 3: While centred on architectural foundations, it also outlines how roles, responsibilities, and data contracts interact across layers, in coordination with complementary tasks (e.g. WP7).

Note 4: It is distinct from the LUMEN Data Model, which provides a semantic alignment layer to support cross-domain interoperability of data product metadata. Together, they ensure both organisational cohesion and semantic integration within the federation.

Resource (or Scientific Resource)

Structured unit of scientific content that can be described, referenced, and potentially reused[21]. Resources may include datasets, publications, software, semantic artefacts, multimedia assets, or any other formal output of scientific activity.

Note 1: In LUMEN, a resource or a set of resources become a data product when it is intentionally selected, documented, and exposed through a data source under a data contract.

Note 2: Not all resources are immediately treated as data products. Some may be under qualification, meaning they are being assessed, enriched, or documented before integration into the federation.

Note 3: This progressive approach allows communities to begin with their most accessible or mature resources, progressively expanding their contributions based on available capacity and priorities.

Note 4: This flexibility enables a pragmatic engagement model, without requiring the immediate formalisation of all potentially reusable resources.

Note 5: Scientific concepts, agents or projects are not considered resources in themselves, unless they are formalised and published as part of a semantic artefact (e.g. ontology, controlled vocabulary, metadata record in a catalog).

Note 6: The term “resource” in the context of LUMEN is equivalent in scope to “research product” as defined in SKG-IF⁴⁹. By extension, it can also describe a data product when complemented with metadata specific to exposure and governance.

Data Product

FAIR, self-contained, and discoverable data asset that encapsulates *data, metadata* and associated governance, designed to deliver measurable value to its users by applying product thinking principles[8].

Note 1: In LUMEN, a data product is a governed package that encapsulates one or more scientific resources that is intentionally exposed by a community or selected for inclusion in order to be reused within the LUMEN federation.

Note 2: A data product becomes part of the LUMEN ecosystem when it is referenced through one or more data sources that expose its metadata in a machine-actionable format.

Note 4: In order to be federated, a data product must be linked to a data contract that defines the conditions of its exposure, governance, and interoperability. While the data contract is conceptually attached to the data product, it also depends on the specific data source through which the product is made accessible, and may vary accordingly.

Data Source

Entity that specifies the components or platform through which a data product is made discoverable, by exposing its structured metadata.

Note 1: A data source may specify a catalogue, repository, registry, or a platform.

Note 2: A data source does not necessarily host the related data products. In the LUMEN context, hosting refers to preserving and serving the actual content of a data product. A data source may simply expose metadata referencing externally hosted content, without guaranteeing access to the data product itself.

Note 3: Data sources may apply validation, enrichment, or formatting policies to the metadata they expose, which may influence the applicable data contract.

Note 4: In the LUMEN data mesh framework, a data contract applies to a specific combination of a data product and the data source from which metadata is exposed.

Data Contract

Structured agreement between a scientific community and the LUMEN federation that specifies an association between a data product and a data source, capturing the specific conditions of exposure and federation.

Note 1: The contract specifies the required metadata schema, data model, controlled vocabularies, and semantic artefacts to ensure the data product is interoperable and discoverable within the federation. It also defines the access conditions, quality expectations, and maintenance practices for the data product, and references one or more data sources through which the data product is made available.

Note 2: In line with EOSC practices[22], different engagement roles can be distinguished within a data contract:

- *Producer:* The community produces and governs the data product directly.

⁴⁹ <https://skg-if.github.io/interoperability-framework/docs/research-product.html>

- *Enhancer*: The community enriches, validates, or curates the metadata of externally hosted data products.
- *Aggregator*: The community aggregates metadata from external sources without editorial curation.
- *Reference*: The community highlights relevant external data products, without assuming responsibility or enrichment.

Note 3: These roles are not mutually exclusive, a single data contract may combine several engagement levels, such as curating aggregated records or referencing enriched external datasets.

Metadata (or Data Product Metadata)

Structured information that describes, contextualises, or enables the discovery, interpretation, and reuse of a data product, including its underlying scientific resources.

Note 1: Data product metadata encompass both the metadata of the underlying scientific resources (e.g. title, author, creation date, licence, format, subject classification, domain-specific attributes, and provenance, in line with the FAIR principles) and additional information describing the data product as a whole (e.g. packaging, exposure, governance, access conditions, operational features such as availability or update frequency).

Note 2: Data product metadata are exposed through standard interfaces and harvested or aligned by common components such as the Meta-Search Engine.

Hosting

Process by which a component stores, preserves, and provides access to the content of a scientific resource in a durable and reliable manner.

Note 1: In the LUMEN context, hosting refers to the custodianship of the actual content of a data product, including its availability and integrity, often under defined preservation and access policies.

Note 2: Hosting may include the assignment of extrinsic persistent identifiers and guarantees regarding long-term accessibility.

Note 3: Hosting differs from exposing, which may reference a data product without storing its content.

Note 4: Hosting is distinct from content replication mechanisms that distribute bitstreams without custodianship or long-term preservation responsibility such as BitTorrent⁵⁰ or IPFS⁵¹.

Exposing

Act of making structured data product metadata accessible through standardised interfaces, in order to support discovery, referencing, and potential reuse across platforms.

Note 1: In the LUMEN context, exposing typically refers to the publication of data product metadata through catalogues, registries, repositories, or platforms, whether or not the content itself is hosted locally.

⁵⁰ https://www.bittorrent.org/beps/bep_0003.html

⁵¹ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3544216.3544232>

Note 2: Referencing is a specific form of exposing, it enables discoverability, citation, and cross-domain linking, while the data product remains under the governance of its canonical provider.

Common Data Model (or LUMEN Data Model)

Data model that defines the core entities, relationships, and metadata attributes used across the federation to describe, publish, and govern data products. It acts as a shared semantic backbone enabling interoperability between communities, platforms, and services, while remaining flexible enough to support domain-specific extensions.

Note 1: The LUMEN Common Data Model defines shared concepts and metadata structures that enable machine-actionable interoperability across heterogeneous standards (e.g. DataCite, schema.org, CodeMeta, TRIPLE Ontology, DCAT, SKG-IF), while supporting semantic mappings between community-specific schemas.

Note 2: It does not represent the operational logic of the data mesh which is defined in the LUMEN Data Mesh Architecture Framework, but it complements it by ensuring that metadata from different sources can be interpreted and queried in a coherent and federated way.

Note 3: This data model will be formalised using standard vocabularies detailed in Deliverable D4.2.

Figure. UML class diagram that illustrates the main data mesh concepts involved in LUMEN

B. Principles

FAIR Principles

Set of guidelines designed to improve the management and stewardship of scientific data and related outputs, by ensuring they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

Note 1: They were introduced by Wilkinson et al. (2016)[23] to promote practices that support machine-actionable metadata, the use of persistent identifiers, adoption of open standards, and clearly defined licences.

Note 2: Within the LUMEN federation, the FAIR Principles underpin the publication and governance of data products, fostering semantic alignment and cross-domain reuse.

Domain Ownership

Principle whereby a designated actor assumes responsibility for the exposure, quality, and alignment of resources associated with a specific scientific community.

Note 1: The owner may be the original data producer (e.g. a research group), a data steward (e.g. a disciplinary infrastructure), or an authorised aggregator (e.g. a thematic catalogue), depending on the resource provenance and governance.

Decentralisation

Architecture model in which control, ownership, and data are distributed across independent entities, without reliance on any central point of coordination.

Note 1: A decentralised system enables each participant to operate autonomously, including managing identifiers, metadata, and services, often using distributed protocols.

Note 2: Decentralisation maximises resilience and independence, but may require greater technical maturity and coordination mechanisms.

Note 3: Full decentralisation implies that no shared technical components, interfaces, or coordination rules exist across participants, each community operates entirely independently, including for discovery, metadata standards, and service orchestration⁵². This is not a target in itself for LUMEN. Instead, LUMEN envisions a progressive move towards decentralisation, enabling communities to increase their autonomy over time. However, the federation is expected to retain certain common components, reference services, and lightweight coordination mechanisms to ensure semantic coherence and sustainable cross-domain interoperability. However, LUMEN does not exclude the possible to integrate decentralised applications⁵³.

Federation (or LUMEN Federation)

Structured collaboration model among autonomous entities that retain their independence and domain ownership while adhering to a common set of principles, protocols, or standards.

Note 1: In a federated model, participants share responsibilities and may interoperate through standardised interfaces, without relying on a central authority.

Note 2: Federation enables alignment (e.g. on metadata, access protocols,

⁵² <https://kevincox.ca/2023/07/20/decentralized-vs-federated/>

⁵³ <https://ethereum.org/en/developers/docs/dapps/>

governance) while allowing each member to use its own infrastructure and maintain local autonomy.

Note 3: LUMEN envisions a federated model as a long-term framework, in which scientific communities are expected to retain autonomy over their data, platforms, and governance practices, while progressively engaging in structured collaboration. The ecosystem is progressively becoming connected through emerging shared components, and coordination mechanisms and alignment efforts, paving the way for structured federation.

Note 4: Federation in LUMEN does not contradict decentralisation⁵⁴. Rather, it provides a structured coordination layer that enables autonomous communities to collaborate through shared protocols, semantic alignment, and data contracts. While some common components are required (e.g. for discovery or governance validation), decentralised capabilities remain in place, and communities retain control over their platforms, data, and integration pace.

C. Communities & Actors

Community (or Scientific Community)

Group of actors organised around a scientific domain and contributing collectively to research data publication, alignment, and governance.

Note 1: A community may include research institutions, disciplinary infrastructures, or expert networks within a defined domain (e.g. Social Sciences and Humanities, Earth System Sciences, Mathematics, Molecular Dynamics).

Note 2: In the LUMEN federation, communities contribute by exposing data products, participating in semantic alignment, entering into data contracts and operating data sources.

Note 3: Each community retains autonomy over its internal platforms and governance but aligns with shared interoperability rules established by the federation.

Note 4: Each community is formally represented within LUMEN by a designated community liaison, who acts as a bridge between the community and the federation, ensuring consistent communication and coordination.

Connected Communities

A transitional state in which scientific communities maintain their own infrastructures and governance but are already engaged in technical and/or semantic exchanges, enabling early alignment, mutual visibility, and shared discovery.

Note 1: In LUMEN, connectedness precedes federation, it describes the initial collaborative layer where communities begin to expose resources, adopt shared protocols, or participate in common components without necessarily formalising their integration through data contracts.

Note 2: The connected state reflects LUMEN's pragmatic and inclusive approach: it acknowledges diverse levels of maturity while facilitating gradual convergence towards structured federation within a data mesh model.

⁵⁴ <https://kevincox.ca/2023/07/20/decentralized-vs-federated/>

Note 3: The expression of intent to join the federation can be captured through lightweight declarations (e.g. community registry entries, onboarding requests, metadata exposure trials), allowing the federation to track and support progressive engagement.

Community Liaison

Designated representative of a scientific community responsible for ensuring coordination, communication, and alignment between the community and the LUMEN federation.

Note 1: The community liaison acts as a point of contact for governance processes, including data contract negotiation, validation, and onboarding activities.

Note 2: This role supports both technical and organisational alignment, ensuring that the community's practices, constraints, and priorities are taken into account in federation decisions.

Note 3: The liaison facilitates the community's engagement with shared services, semantic alignment efforts, and interoperability mechanisms defined within the federation.

Note 4: Each scientific community participating in LUMEN should formally appoint a community liaison as part of its contribution to federated governance.

Technical Coordinator

Expert appointed within the federation to support technical alignment, operational coordination, and onboarding of scientific communities.

Note 1: Technical Coordinators are not necessarily affiliated with a specific scientific community. They may belong to the LUMEN core team, a work package, or a service development unit.

Note 2: They work in tandem with Community Liaisons to ensure that technical requirements (e.g. metadata exposure, API integration, contract compliance) are met during federation onboarding.

Note 3: Within the Guild, Technical Coordinators contribute to the evaluation of technical feasibility, tool interoperability, and alignment with the federation architecture.

Note 4: Their role is instrumental in ensuring that cross-community services evolve consistently with the federation's standards and implementation roadmap.

Guild (or Community Guild)

Governance body composed of formally designated representatives from participating scientific communities and technical coordinators, tasked with collectively steering the evolution, validation, and alignment processes within the LUMEN federation.

Note 1: In LUMEN, the guild ensures distributed governance by providing a structured space where decisions related to eligibility rules, validation of data contracts, onboarding processes, and alignment with EOSC standards are discussed and agreed upon.

Note 2: Each participating community is represented by its community liaison, who acts as the primary delegate within the guild. Technical coordination is ensured by WP leaders or designated experts.

Note 3: The detailed procedures for decision-making, conflict resolution, and policy endorsement will be defined and formalised under Task 7.4.

Note 4: The term “guild” reflects a peer-based and participatory governance model, emphasising trust, shared responsibility, and progressive alignment over hierarchical enforcement.

Figure. UML class diagram that illustrates the key organisational actors in the LUMEN federation

D. Scientific Resources

Individual

Entity representing a natural person involved in the creation, curation, or stewardship of scientific resources.

Note 1: In LUMEN, individuals are typically represented through author profiles, including their identifiers (e.g. ORCID), affiliations, and scientific outputs.

Organisation

Entity representing a structured group or institution (e.g. university, research institute, consortium) that participates in scientific activities or manages resources.

Note 1: Organisations may act as authors, publishers, or providers of data products and services.

Agent

Entity (either an individual or an organisation) primarily responsible for the intellectual content or creation of a scientific resource.⁵⁵

Note 1: In LUMEN, authorship may be attributed to persons (e.g. researchers) or organisations (e.g. departments, user groups), depending on the provenance of the resource.

Agent profile

A structured metadata record that describes the identity, affiliations, expertise areas, and contributions of an agent (individual or organisation) involved in scientific activities.

Note 1: Author profiles typically include references to research literature, datasets, software, projects, or other scholarly outputs.

Note 2: Author profiles typically describe individual persons (e.g. researchers), but may also refer to organisations (e.g. research groups, departments) when they act as collective authors.

Note 3: In the LUMEN context, author profiles may be created manually by users (as in platforms like GoTriple⁵⁶), or sourced from external systems such as ORCID, institutional directories, or domain-specific platforms like zbMATH Open⁵⁷.

Note 4: This definition aligns with schema.org/Person⁵⁸ and schema.org/Organization⁵⁹, both of which can be used as the value of the author property in metadata descriptions.

Note 5: Agent profile records are not considered data products by default, as they primarily provide contextual, relational, or provenance information. However, if they are exposed as curated, governed, and reusable units (e.g. structured registries of expert agents), they may be formalised as data products in LUMEN, under conditions of governance, exposure, and reuse.

Research Literature

Scientific resource that formally communicates research findings through textual or visual content disseminated via recognised academic channels[24].

Note 1: Research literature include journal articles, conference papers, preprints, technical reports, and other scholarly outputs intended for peer communication and citation.

Dataset

Scientific resource consisting of a structured collection of data, organised in a defined format, and intended to be analysed, processed, or reused in support of scientific research.

Note 1: A dataset may take the form of tabular, hierarchical, multidimensional, or temporal collections, depending on disciplinary practices. For instance, in Earth System Sciences, datasets often include sensor-based time series and satellite

⁵⁵ <https://lambdamusic.github.io/ontospy-examples/foaf/foafagent.html>

⁵⁶ <https://gotriple.eu/about>

⁵⁷ See for example <https://zbmath.org/authors/noether.emmy>

⁵⁸ <https://schema.org/Person>

⁵⁹ <https://schema.org/Organization>

observations; in Molecular Dynamics, structured simulation outputs and molecular trajectory files; in Mathematics, curated benchmark datasets used to test algorithms or formal proofs; and in SSH, corpora of textual sources, survey data, or multilingual bibliographic records harvested from discovery platforms like GoTriple.

Note 2: In LUMEN, a dataset becomes a data product when it is intentionally selected, documented, and published under FAIR conditions for discovery and reuse.

Note 3: Not all datasets qualify immediately as data products; some may require additional documentation, validation, or alignment with federation eligibility criteria.

Note 4: Georeferenced datasets, i.e. datasets that include spatial information such as coordinates, bounding boxes, or geometries, are also considered scientific resources in LUMEN.

Software

Scientific resource composed of source code, scripts, libraries, or executable programs designed to perform computational tasks or support research workflows[25].

Note 1: Software may include research code, analytical pipelines, simulation engines, or reusable libraries, and can be written in various programming languages.

Semantic Artefact

Scientific resource that provides a structured, machine-actionable and readable formalisation of a conceptualisation that enables the sharing and reuse by humans and machines⁶⁰. They may vary in complexity, from loose sets of terms to formal ontologies. While they are often serialised in RDF-based formats (e.g. RDF Turtle, OWL, JSON-LD), other representations (e.g. XML, CSV, JSON) may also be used, provided they support machine-actionable semantics.

Note 1: Entities may be formalised within semantic artefacts to enable interoperability, discovery, and semantic alignment across metadata and other scientific resources.

Multimedia asset

Scientific resource consisting of non-textual content such as images, audio recordings, video footage, or visualisations that support or document research activities.

Note 1: Multimedia assets may serve as primary research materials (e.g. field recordings, microscopy images) or as derived illustrations (e.g. visualisations, diagrams) accompanying scientific outputs.

Project

Structured scientific activity undertaken to address a defined research objective, typically constrained by time, funding, and institutional or collaborative frameworks.

Note 1: Projects may produce various scientific resources

Note 2: Project records are not considered data products by default, as they typically serve as contextual or provenance information. However, in cases where projects are exposed as reusable, well-described units (e.g. structured project registries, linked

⁶⁰ See FAIRsFAIR (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4314320>) and EOSC Interoperability Framework: (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10518860>)

research contexts), they may be formalised as data products within LUMEN, provided they meet the criteria of governance, exposure, and reuse, especially when provided by platforms such as GoTriple⁶¹.

Molecule

A structured scientific object representing a chemical or biological entity, typically identified through a name, formula, or structural representation, and used in research contexts such as molecular dynamics, structural biology, or material science.

Note 1: A molecule is not a scientific resource per se; however, when described in a structured, reusable form (e.g. with metadata, structure files, or ontological annotations), it may be included in data products, especially in computational science workflows.

Note 2: This definition is introduced in LUMEN in response to concrete modelling needs expressed by the Molecular Dynamics community, where molecules are treated as key reference objects for structuring and interlinking simulation outputs.

Note 3: Molecules may be extracted from datasets, referenced in research literature, or generated via simulations. In LUMEN, they are treated as identifiable scientific objects that can support semantic alignment and reuse across platforms.

Figure. UML class diagram that illustrates key Scientific Resources in LUMEN
 This diagram presents the main types of scientific resources and their conceptual relationships within the LUMEN framework.

⁶¹ <https://gotriple.eu/about>

E. Conceptual Architecture

Layer

A conceptual level within an architecture that organises related responsibilities, functions, or components into a coherent group, often corresponding to a distinct concern or role in the architecture.

Note 1: In the context of the LUMEN data mesh Framework, the architecture is structured around three conceptual layers: the Connected Communities Ecosystem (decentralised domain-specific infrastructures and actors), the Common Discovery Infrastructure (shared technical enablers for cross-domain alignment) and the Federated Shared Data Governance (rules, roles, and contracts ensuring coherent operation across the ecosystem).

Connected Communities Ecosystem

Decentralised layer of the LUMEN data mesh Framework, composed of connected communities that manage their own infrastructures, platforms, and governance, while progressively engaging in collaboration and alignment with the federation.

Note 1: Each community operates its own domain-specific platforms and may expose data products through standardised interfaces.

Note 2: Communities may differ in their levels of maturity, technical capacity, and engagement. The ecosystem supports this diversity by promoting gradual convergence through shared protocols, open standards, and community liaison mechanisms.

Note 3: This layer reflects the principle of domain-oriented ownership at the core of the data mesh paradigm. It provides the foundation for interoperability and reuse without imposing centralisation.

Common Discovery Infrastructure

Layer of the LUMEN data mesh Framework, composed of all interoperable components, platforms, and services designed to support cross-domain discovery, alignment, and access to data products across the LUMEN federation.

Note 1: It provides a common interoperability layer between connected community platforms, enabling metadata alignment, semantic enrichment, and search interoperability.

Note 2: This infrastructure includes both deployable components (e.g. metadata broker, semantic services), integrated platforms (e.g. the White Label Platform, Lumis), and cross-cutting services (e.g. meta-search engine, AI assistant), supporting convergence, scalability, and service federation.

Note 3: In the LUMEN architecture, these components form the intermediate layer between the connected community infrastructures and the governance framework, supporting both technical convergence and scalability.

Note 4: The name “Common Discovery Infrastructure” reflects the inclusion of complex platforms and deployed services, not just technical components.

Federated Shared Data Governance

Layer of the LUMEN Data Mesh Framework, composed of shared roles, rules, and processes defined and enacted by autonomous communities to ensure coherence, interoperability, and trust across the federation.

Note 1: It defines the conditions under which data products are validated, integrated, and maintained in the mesh, without centralised control.

Note 2: Governance is enacted through the community guild, which brings together community liaisons and technical coordinators to validate data contracts, define eligibility criteria, and align with EOSC frameworks, such as those described in the EOSC Federation Handbook[26].

Note 3: This layer supports distributed accountability, enabling diverse communities to participate under shared but non-imposing rules.

Note 4: The roles, rules, and processes will be formalised under Task 7.4.

Component

Functional building block that implements a specific function contributing to data discovery, exposure, or interoperability.

Note 1: In LUMEN, components are designed to be modular, interoperable, and aligned with FAIR principles.

Note 2: Components can be deployed independently or integrated within community platforms, depending on specific use cases and needs.

Service

Concrete function provided by a component and made accessible through a defined interface, enabling a specific operation on data products.

Note 1: Services may be offered by community platforms or common components, and may target different aspects of a data product, including its resource content (e.g. transformation, download, annotation), its metadata (e.g. deduplicate, validation, enrichment), or its usage context (e.g. discovery, search, exploration).

Note 2: A service is distinct from the component that implements it, and from the interface through which it is accessed.

Note 3: To ensure traceability, reliability, and governance, services should be described using structured properties, such as operator, availability period, performance indicators, and reliability level.

Note 4: The governance and monitoring of services will be progressively defined and formalised as part of the activities in WP7.

Interface

Defined point of interaction through which a platform, component, or service makes functionalities or resources and data products accessible to users or other platforms.

Note 1: Interfaces may be human-facing (e.g. graphical user interfaces, search portals) or machine-actionable (e.g. REST APIs, SPARQL endpoints).

Note 2: Interfaces provide the access layer to services and components, ensuring usability, discoverability, and interoperability.

Note 3: In LUMEN, machine-actionable interfaces are critical for exposing data products in a reusable and standardised way, as specified in the corresponding data

contracts.

Note 4: The design and documentation of interfaces must align with federation rules and supported protocols to ensure consistent integration.

Protocol

Formal specification of rules and formats governing the exchange of information between platforms, components, or services.

Note 1: Protocols define how data is transmitted, requested, or exposed through interfaces, ensuring syntactic and semantic interoperability.

Note 2: In LUMEN, protocols such as REST, CSW, OAI-PMH, MOD-API or semantic interoperability frameworks like SKG-IF⁶² are used to enable harvesting, querying, and data access across heterogeneous platforms.

Note 3: Protocol support is a key eligibility criterion for data sources participating in the federation.

Note 4: Protocols ensure that interfaces can interact reliably and consistently within the data mesh infrastructure.

Platform (or Portal)

Concrete configuration designed to support a specific domain, community, or use case by integrating multiple components and services into a coherent operational environment.

Note 1: In LUMEN, platforms serve as entry points for users and communities to interact with data products, and may support workflows for discovery, enrichment, or search or visualisation.

Note 2: A platform may be domain-specific (e.g. GoTriple for Social Sciences and Humanities) or domain-agnostic (e.g. the White-Label Discovery Platform, deployable by any community).

Note 3: A platform may include or interact with other platforms, depending on its intended functions and integration within the federation.

Note 4: Platforms are key operational units in the LUMEN federation, and their availability, reliability, and alignment with federation rules may be subject to governance mechanisms defined in WP7.

Note 5: Some core discovery assets, such as the White-Label Discovery Platform, are designed to be deployed as platforms by communities, integrating additional services and interfaces according to local needs.

Catalogue

Components designed to support the discovery, access, and governance of scientific resources. It aggregates structured metadata and may integrate various roles such as describing resources (registry), hosting them (repository), or exposing them for discovery and reuse.

Note 1: In LUMEN, a catalogue can take multiple forms: as a metadata aggregator, it collects and harmonises descriptions of resources from diverse sources. As a

62

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/scientific-knowledge-graphs-interoperability-framework-skg-if-wg/activity/>

registry, it serves as an authoritative reference of entities (e.g. authors, vocabularies, software components) without necessarily hosting the underlying resource. As a repository, it provides access to actual content (e.g. datasets, software packages, publications) with persistent identifiers and FAIR-compliant metadata.

Note 2: While these roles can be conceptually distinguished, they often overlap in practice. Many catalogues provide a combination of discovery, metadata registration, and access to resources.

Note 3: This inclusive definition reflects the pragmatic approach adopted in LUMEN, aiming to reduce unnecessary fragmentation. It aligns with discussions in the community[27] suggesting that many FAIR-oriented infrastructures already blur the lines between these roles and that the term “catalogue” may serve as a useful umbrella when distinctions are not essential for the user.

Figure. UML class diagram that illustrates key elements of the LUMEN Conceptual Architecture

F. Core Discovery Assets

Core Discovery Asset

Key interoperable element of the LUMEN Common Discovery Infrastructure layer that provides essential capabilities for the discovery, alignment, or access to data products across the federation.

Note 1: A Core Discovery Asset may take the form of a component (modular function), a platform (deployed configuration integrating multiple components), or a service (operational interface accessible to users or machines).

Note 2: These assets constitute the operational backbone of the Common Discovery Infrastructure, including the White-Label Platform, the Meta-Search, and LUMIS.

Note 3: The term “asset” is used to avoid ambiguities related to architectural granularity, and to accommodate diverse technical implementations under a unified conceptual layer.

White-Label Discovery Platform

Reusable discovery component designed to be deployed as a platform and configured by individual communities to expose and explore data products in alignment with LUMEN federation principles.

Note 1: The platform can be instantiated as a standalone platform operated by communities and provides discovery services such as search, filtering, visualisation, and metadata annotation, based on shared interfaces and semantic alignment mechanisms.

Note 2: As a core discovery asset of the LUMEN architecture, the White-Label Discovery Platform plays a key role in enabling decentralised discovery across the federation. It supports the exposure of data products by multiple communities through shared discovery mechanisms, semantic alignment, and interoperable interfaces.

Note 3: Each instance can be configured to reflect local branding, domain-specific vocabularies, and community-specific rules while remaining interoperable through standard protocols.

Note 4: When deployed, the White-Label Platform also acts as a data source because it exposes structured metadata describing resources related to data products.

LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics (or LUMIS)

Platform and set of services designed to support the creation, validation, curation, publication, and reuse of semantic artefacts in a machine-actionable, interoperable, and FAIR-compliant manner.

Note 1: In LUMEN, the LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics provides shared services for creating, registering, versioning, validating, and exposing semantic artefacts in standard formats (e.g. RDF, OWL, SKOS).

Note 2: As a core discovery asset of the LUMEN architecture, it plays a key role in enabling semantic interoperability across platforms and communities, and supports the alignment of local practices with federation-wide standards.

Note 3: The space is integrated into the LUMEN architecture through standard interfaces and governance mechanisms, allowing both centralised and community-managed contributions.

Meta-Search (or Meta-Search Engine)

Component or platform that enables discovery and cross-domain querying of data products exposed by LUMEN communities.

Note 1: The Meta-Search Engine primarily indexes data product metadata, published by communities.

Note 2: When metadata is exposed by communities alongside data products, either embedded or through declared endpoints, the Meta-Search Engine may support their indexing and querying, depending on their structure and interoperability level.

Note 3: The Meta-Search Engine does not store the data products or their internal content, but acts as a discovery layer supporting reuse, linking, and integration across the federation.

Note 4: As a core discovery asset of the LUMEN architecture, the Meta-Search Engine plays a central role in enabling distributed discovery across the federation. It provides the foundation for shared search services and powers the White-Label Discovery Platform and other domain-specific platforms.

